

Natural History Collections Imaging Survey Report

Current imaging practices across institutions worldwide

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A MOBILISE/iDigBio Report

September, 2023

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme
of the European Union

This report is based upon work from COST Action CA 17106 MOBILISE, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology), and in collaboration with iDigBio.

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Suggested citation: Marcer A., Santos J., Mast A., Nelson G., Ellwood L. and Has-ton E. (2023). Natural History Collections Imaging Survey Report. Current imag-ing practices across institutions worldwide. MOBILISE EU Cost Action CA1706. <http://10.5281/zenodo.7837354>

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

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Contents

1	Background & Objectives	6
2	Summary of key findings	7
2.0.1	Respondents' overall profile	7
2.0.2	Standards awareness and use	7
2.0.3	Obstacles to the use of standards	8
2.0.4	General comments	8
3	Methodology	10
4	Results	11
4.1	Respondents	11
4.1.1	By country	11
4.1.2	By role	12
4.1.3	By institution size	13
4.1.4	By preparation type	14
4.2	Collections	14
4.2.1	Overall	14
4.2.2	By taxonomic group	15
4.2.3	By country	16
4.3	Standards awareness	16
4.3.1	Overall	16
4.3.2	By country	17
4.3.3	By institution size	18
4.3.4	By role	19
4.4	Standards use	20
4.4.1	Overall	20
4.4.2	Awareness versus use	21
4.4.3	By country	22
4.4.4	By role	23
4.5	Obstacles	24
4.5.1	Overall	24
4.5.2	By country	24
4.5.3	By institution size	25
4.5.4	By preparation type	26
4.5.5	By collection type	26
4.5.6	By collection size	27
4.6	Preparation types	27

4.6.1	By country	27
4.6.2	By collection type	28
4.6.3	By collection size	29
4.7	Image content	30
4.7.1	Elements included	30
4.7.2	Image kinds	31
4.8	Image format	33
4.8.1	Format	33
4.9	Image quality	35
4.9.1	Colour (bit) depth	35
4.9.2	Colour space	36
4.9.3	Colour calibration	37
4.9.4	Image sharpening	38
4.9.5	Colour correction	39
4.9.6	Image cropping	40
4.10	Image metadata	41
4.10.1	Standards	41
4.10.2	Storage	42
4.10.3	Profiles	43
4.10.3.1	HERBARIUM SHEETS	43
4.10.3.2	LIQUID PRESERVED	50
4.10.3.3	MICROSCOPE SLIDES	53
4.10.3.4	DRIED AND PINNED	55
4.10.3.5	DRIED AND ASSEMBLED	58
4.10.3.6	DRIED NOT ASSEMBLED	60
4.10.3.7	FOSSILS 2D	63
4.10.3.8	FOSSILS 3D	66
4.10.3.9	GEOLOGICAL MACROOBJECTS	69
	Acknowledgements	71
5	Appendix 1 - List of institutions	73
6	Appendix 2 - Comments	81
7	Appendix 3 - Survey Questionnaire	89
8	Appendix 4 - List of standards and guidelines	100

1 Background & Objectives

The rapid development of processes for digital imaging Natural History Collections around the world has resulted in a wide range of equipment, protocols and standards for capturing images of the diverse range of specimen objects in the collections.

Some of the guidelines have been developed for digital imaging in general by the Universal Photographic Digital Imaging Guidelines coalition, or for cultural collection objects and archives by the Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative and the Digital Preservation Coalition. Others have been developed more specifically for Natural History collections by JSTOR Global Plants, New York Botanic Garden (NYBG), the Integrated Digitized Biocollections (iDigBio) programme, the Atlas of Living Australia (ALA) and the EU-funded Innovation and Consolidation for Large-scale Digitisation of Natural Heritage (ICEDIG) project.

Whilst these guidelines and recommendations have been developed for many of the object types held in natural history collections, it has not been clear how widely these have been taken up and used by the community. Here, we present the results of an international survey that was undertaken to build a comprehensive overview of awareness and implementation of standards, best practice guidelines and protocols for imaging natural history specimens and to identify impediments that institutions face when applying existing standards and making the images available online. The survey was designed and constructed jointly by members of the EU-funded COST Action, MOBILISE, and the US-funded iDigBio programme, and distributed globally to gather information from as many institutions and individuals as possible.

The survey covered all types of curated natural history specimens held in institutions (museums, botanical gardens, universities, research institutes, biological stations) across the world, and was structured around the kind of specimen (preparation type) to facilitate responses from each institution. Each respondent had an option to limit their response to a basic set of high level questions about the institution collections and digitisation progress, priorities and obstacles and awareness/use of standards and guidelines, or to expand their response to a more detailed set of technical questions about protocols and standards.

The survey was meant to be the basis for discussion in a future workshop that took place in Heraklion, Crete, in June 2022. The results of the survey are presented in this report.

2 Summary of key findings

Following is a summary of the main findings of the survey, which was answered by a total of 702 respondents. For a detailed analysis of the results of the survey please refer to the following sections.

2.0.1 Respondents' overall profile

1. Most of the answers came from institutions in North and Central America, representing about 39% of all answers, followed by Europe with 32%, South America with 11%, Asia with 8%, Africa with 6%, and Oceania with 4%.
2. The questionnaire was mainly answered by people whose institutional role was that of *Curator*, *Collection manager* or *Researcher*, in that order.
3. About 50% of the responding institutions report having 100 000 specimens or less, while, on the other end of the spectrum, about 24% report holding 1 000 000 specimens or more.
4. There is a very large gap between preparation types. *Herbarium sheets* comprise 61.5% of the responses, followed by *Dried - not assembled* which constituted only 8.8% of the responses. Only 5 answers corresponded to *Geological macro-objects*.
5. The most reported combination of preparation and collection types was that of *Herbarium sheets* and *Botany / Algae / Fungi* with about 53% of the responses, followed by *Dried and pinned* and *Zoology (Invertebrates)* with a 5.4% of respondents. In the first case, collection sizes had a median of 25 000 specimens and a maximum of 7 800 000, and in the second case a median of 500 000 and a maximum of 17 000 000.
6. Across all responses, collection sizes had a median of 35 000, a mean of 658 366 and a maximum of 30 000 000.

2.0.2 Standards awareness and use

1. The iDigBio Recommendations and DROID series represent the standards most widely known with a 19.9% of the respondents acknowledging their awareness, followed by the *DiSSCo ICEDIG series* with a 16.2%. The higher awareness of the *iDigBio* standards over the *DiSSCo* ones might in part be due to the fact that the latter have been published much later (see Appendix 4). Remarkably though, a 29.1% of the respondents reported not being aware of any of the standards. This pattern holds when considering the use of standards, except for the fact that the *DiSSCo ICEDIG series* is less used than known.

2. In terms of widespread use across countries, *JSTOR* and *NYBG* standards are the most known and used. In the case of the *JSTOR* standards, this may be due to the fact that they are among the earliest to have been published.
3. There is a big gap between the knowledge of the existence of standards and their actual use, and that is true for all standards, suggesting an impediment of some kind to their adoption.
4. Smaller institutions are generally less aware than bigger ones of the existence of standards.
5. There are no significant differences between institutional roles played by the respondents and their awareness and use of standards.

2.0.3 Obstacles to the use of standards

1. The *Lack of staff time*, *Financial*, and *Lack of equipment* obstacles to using standards represent over 50% of all responses. Only 2.4% of the respondents report having *No obstacles present*.
2. There is not a clear difference between the kinds of obstacles reported by different countries.
3. *Financial* and *Lack of staff time* are predominant in larger institutions while *Lack of equipment* prevails in small institutions.
4. *Lack of staff time* is reported as the biggest constraint for most preparation and collection types.
5. The distribution of collection sizes is similar across obstacles.

2.0.4 General comments

1. Many respondents reflected on the general lack of resources (money, staff, time, ...) as an impediment to the digitisation of their collections. Hence, they prioritise curation and databasing.
2. In order to overcome the general lack of resources, an interesting option was raised, based on the possibility of pooling resources among several institutions to centralise digitisation infrastructure for the collective use.
3. Respondents also called for guidance on imaging, file storage and metadata.
4. A direct simple benefit of the survey has been that of providing the list of available standards, helping in making them more visible to collections' staff. Respondents were grateful for this.

5. The need for a consensed gold standard to replace the multitude of standards was also pointed out.

3 Methodology

We organized our questionnaire in two main sections (see [Appendix 3 - Survey Questionnaire](#)): a section aimed at gathering basic institutional information and a section on imaging practices. The latter section was itself organized into two distinct parts. A first part aimed at discovering the overall awareness on the existence of imaging standards, and a second part where we asked information regarding aspects such as collection types and sizes, standards used, obstacles that hindered imaging, and image content, format, quality, and metadata, for a list of preparation types (*e.g. Herbarium sheets, microscope slides, etc.*). The questionnaire allowed respondents to answer for up to ten different preparation types. We also left a final section for expressing any further comments. The questionnaire had a total of 30 questions if answered for just one preparation type, and 22 repeated questions for any extra preparation type the respondent wished to answer. The questionnaire could be completed anonymously but respondents were able to specify their institution and email if desired. The estimated time to complete the survey was between 5 and 10 minutes per preparation type.

On April 8, 2022, we invited through email a total of 5428 people, playing diverse roles within institutions holding natural history collections, to answer the survey (see [Appendix 3 - Survey Questionnaire](#)). We also posted the link to the survey to other forums such as the NHCOLL-L discussion list of the Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections, and to the iDigBio and DiSSCo mailing lists. We closed the survey at the end of June 2022.

We chose [SurveyMonkey](#) for conducting the survey. Once completed, we downloaded all individual responses as a csv file and performed all analyses using the R Computing Environment [1].

4 Results

4.1 Respondents

The survey was answered by a total of 702 respondents from 640 declared institutions from all continents except for Antarctica.

4.1.1 By country

The country with the most respondents was the United States with 216 respondents, followed by Brazil with 37 and Canada and the United Kingdom with 25 each.

Figure 1: Respondents by country

Number of respondents per country United States 216, Brazil 37, Canada 25, United Kingdom 25, Spain 23, India 20, Italy 20, Colombia 19, Australia 15, France 15, Germany 13, Philippines 13, Portugal 13, Sweden 13, Mexico 12, Switzerland 11, Argentina 10, New Zealand 10, South Africa 10, Russia 9, Pakistan 7, Czech Republic 6, Ecuador 6, Estonia 6, Netherlands 6, Uganda 6, Austria 5, Belgium 5, Bulgaria 5, China 5, Albania 4, Indonesia 4, Nigeria 4, Poland 4, Turkey 4, Denmark 3, Finland 3, Hungary 3, Ireland 3, Japan 3, Malaysia 3, Tanzania 3, Thailand 3, Ukraine 3, Afghanistan 2, Bangladesh 2, Belarus 2, Benin 2, Bolivia 2, Costa Rica 2, Greece 2, Israel 2, Ivory Coast 2, Kenya 2, Luxembourg 2, Norway 2, Oman 2, Panama 2, Peru 2, Romania 2, Slovakia 2, Sri Lanka 2, Tunisia 2, Bahamas 1, Barbados 1, Botswana 1, Chile 1, Croatia 1, Cuba 1, Cyprus 1, Dominican Republic 1, El Salvador 1, Guatemala 1, Iran 1, Jordan 1, Lithuania 1, Madagascar 1, Morocco 1, Namibia 1, Nicaragua 1, North Macedonia 1, Rwanda 1,

Singapore 1, Slovenia 1, South Korea 1, Sudan 1, Suriname 1, Taiwan 1, Tajikistan 1, United Arab Emirates 1, Uruguay 1, Venezuela 1, Vietnam 1, Zimbabwe 1

4.1.2 By role

The institutional role played by most respondents was that of Curator, followed by Collection manager and Researcher. The role closest to the handling of the specimen for imaging, i.e. Digitiser, was only the 6th out of 7 roles considered.

Figure 2: Respondents by role

Other reported roles: Academia — Academic Professor/volunteer curator — academic teacher — adjunct professor — Archives Assistant — Arkansas herbarium digitization coordinator — assistant curator of Herbarium CESJ — assistant professor — Assistant Professor and Curator — Assistant Professor and Curator of Fungi — Assistant Professor, Herbarium keeper — Associate Curator — Associate Professor — Biodiversity Information Coordinator — Biology Professor and Herbarium Director (but I do collection mgmt, curation, etc. It’s a one person show) — Chair of Biology Department — Chief Director: Foundational Biodiversity Science — Co-curator — Collections Assistant — Collections Officer — company — Correspondent — Data manager — Data Scientist — Database Administrator — Database Manager — Department Head Life Sciences — Deputy Director of collections — Digital curator - supervising digitisation — Digital Repository Manager — Digitisation Manager — Digitisation operations manager — Digitization Asset Manager — Digitization Manager — Digitization Program Manager — Director — Director of Granite Mountains Desert Research Center (Univ. of California, Riverside) — discco coord — DiSSCo National Node coordinator — Emeritus faculty — Emeritus Professor of Biology — En Colombia como en muchos países Latinoamericanos, no hay un grupo grande trabajando en Colecciones, yo soy la Curadora, y debo hacer de todo. — Executive Director — Extension specialist — faculty — Faculty Member

— Food Analyst — Full professor — Head Collection Management — Head Curator — Head Gardener — Head of collections — Head of Department — Head of herbarium and library — Head of Projects Department — Head of Science program and Chief Botanist — Head/General Manager — Herbarium Digitisation Manager — Herbarium Technician — I am a Pro-bono Associate Curator of the UTCEC herbarium — I am a retired Professor Emeritus but still curator for the Herbarium BAR — I'm a teacher & researcher. There isn't an official position to manage the collection. Only volunteer. — Identification and documentation of plant specimens of different organs — In charge of the herbarium (BLMPR) — Laboratory in charge, Botany cum Herbarium — lecturer — Librarian — Manager digitisation — Manager Digitization — Masters candidate — Meritorious Professor, Dean, principal investigator — Museum Director — Ornithology Collection Manager — Photo Archivist — Private sector supported Project assistant Data Mobilization — Profesional Adjunto (CPA) - Encargada de colecciones neontológicas — Professor — Professor (teach classes) — professor and research — Professor and volunteer — Records officer — Registrar — researcher — Retired Department Head — Science Director — Scientific curator — Scientific responsible of the Herbario SEV — Scientific Secretary (in charge of collection manager) — Scientist and Head of Office — Seed Bank Official — Senior lecturer — staff curator — Staff Member — State Government Entomologist — System owner specimen information and digitisation — Teacher — Team Leader for group with responsibility for xylaria — Technical staff — Technical staff - backlog — Technical staff - biologist — University educator — Urban forester — Visitng Scientist — We have a full-time staff of one, so I am responsible for ALL tasks typically associated with a natural history collection: collection management, database management, recruiting/training/supervising student hourly workers, leading tours, outreach, etc., etc.... — Working as Assistant Professor along with involved in management of Dr. Sultan Ahmed Herbarium which has rare plant specimens of century old collections

4.1.3 By institution size

Roughly, the higher the size of an institution the lower the number of respondents which is in consonance with the unequal distribution of institution sizes worldwide, where there are many more small-sized institutions than large ones.

Figure 3: Respondents by institution size

4.1.4 By preparation type

In accordance with taxonomic groups reported, the survey is biased towards Herbarium sheets, which represent 61.5% of all responses. Following are Dried - not assembled (8.8%), Dried and pinned (7%) and Liquid preserved (5.8 %). The rest of types constitute altogether a 9%, and Other types a final 7.9%.

Figure 4: Respondents by preparation type

4.2 Collections

4.2.1 Overall

Collection sizes spread across a large range, from very small collections in the order of units to the largest collection of in the order of 30 million specimens. The quartiles for the distribution of sizes are as follows: Q1=5 000, Q2=35 000, Q3=300 000. At the extremes,

there are 69 reported collections of 1000 specimens or less and 80 collections of 1 000 000 specimens or more.

Figure 5: Collection size

4.2.2 By taxonomic group

The survey responses are very biased towards *Botany / Algae / Fungi*, which represent over 62.4% of all responses. Second are *Zoology (Invertebrates)* specimens with a 62.4% and, third, *Zoology (Vertebrates)* specimens with a 62.4%. The least represented are *Microorganisms* with only a 1.3%.

Figure 6: Collections by taxonomic group

4.2.3 By country

The number of countries reporting collections for the three most reported taxonomic groups are: *Botany / Algae / Fungi* with 81, *Zoology (Invertebrates)* with 22, and *Zoology (Vertebrates)* with 17.

Figure 7: Collections by country

4.3 Standards awareness

4.3.1 Overall

The three best known standards were: *DISSCO ICEDIG* reported by 16.2 respondents, *JSTOR* reported by 11.8 respondents, and *iDigBio DROID* reported by 10.9 respondents. A 29.1% of respondents reported not being aware of any standard.

Within the *DISSCO* series of standards, the number of respondents that reported being aware of each one were: *ICEDIG Deliverable 3.1*: 31, *ICEDIG Deliverable 3.2*: 29, *ICEDIG Deliverable 3.3*: 24, *ICEDIG Deliverable 3.4*: 28, *ICEDIG Deliverable 3.5*: 24, *ICEDIG Deliverable 3.6*: 51, *ICEDIG Deliverable 3.7*: 24. Within the *iDigBio* series of standards, the number of respondents that reported being aware of each one were: *iDigBio DROID 1*: 54, *iDigBio DROID 2*: 29, *iDigBio DROID 3*: 31, *iDigBio DROID 4*: 28.

Figure 8: Standard awareness

ALA: ALA Guidance: Digitisation: A strategic approach for natural history collections; DPC: Digital Preservation Coalition Handbook; DISSCO ICEDIG: DISSCO ICEDIG project deliverables 1 through 7; FADGI: Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative; iDigBio Recommendations: iDigBio Recommendations for the Acquisition, Processing, and Archiving of Digital Media; iDigBio DROID: iDigBio Developing Robust Object Image to Data series, 1 through 4; NYBG: NYBG Herbarium Specimen Imaging: Standards and Suggestions; JSTOR: JSTOR Global Plants guidelines; UPDIG: Universal Photographic Digital Imaging Guidelines.

Links to all these documents can be found in Appendix 3 under question number 5 in the Survey Questionnaire.

4.3.2 By country

Independently of the number of times they have been reported in each country by different institutions, the standard with the most widespread use is *JSTOR* with 50 countries reported, followed by *NYBG* with 42 and *DISSCO ICEDIG* with 37.

Figure 9: Standard awareness by country

4.3.3 By institution size

Smaller institutions are generally less aware of standards than larger institutions; the percentage of respondents, relative to each role, which report knowledge of standards is noticeably lower for those from smaller institutions than for those at larger institutions. The average percentage of standard awareness across the different standards for each institution size diminishes in accordance with institution size. Also, larger institutions have a more consistent knowledge of all standards while the knowledge of standards at smaller institutions tends to depend more on the given standard, i.e. NYBG and JSTOR are much better known than the rest of the standards. Finally, the percentage of respondents that are not aware of any standard increases as institution size decreases.

Institution size	Not known	37.5 (3)		25 (2)		12.5 (1)						50 (4)
	> 10M	35.3 (18)	9.8 (5)	33.3 (17)	19.6 (10)	39.2 (20)	37.3 (19)	13.7 (7)	21.6 (11)	5.9 (3)		31.4 (16)
	5M to < 10M	18.8 (6)	9.4 (3)	12.5 (4)	12.5 (4)	37.5 (12)	21.9 (7)	34.4 (11)	28.1 (9)	3.1 (1)		37.5 (12)
	1M to < 5M	22.1 (19)	8.1 (7)	12.8 (11)	5.8 (5)	25.6 (22)	18.6 (16)	31.4 (27)	40.7 (35)	5.8 (5)		32.6 (28)
	500K to < 1M	5.1 (3)	10.2 (6)	5.1 (3)	3.4 (2)	22 (13)	6.8 (4)	20.3 (12)	33.9 (20)	3.4 (2)		45.8 (27)
	100K to < 500K	6.6 (8)	3.3 (4)	4.9 (6)	0.8 (1)	14.8 (18)	7.4 (9)	19.7 (24)	28.7 (35)	1.6 (2)		48.4 (59)
	50K to < 100K	8.2 (5)	3.3 (2)	4.9 (3)		11.5 (7)	4.9 (3)	21.3 (13)	8.2 (5)			67.2 (41)
	10K to < 50K	3.6 (5)	3.6 (5)	5.7 (8)	0.7 (1)	9.3 (13)	5.7 (8)	15 (21)	11.4 (16)	0.7 (1)		70 (98)
	< 10K	6.3 (9)	4.2 (6)	6.3 (9)	2.1 (3)	7.7 (11)	4.2 (6)	18.9 (27)	15.4 (22)	2.8 (4)		65.7 (94)
		ALA	DPC	ICEDIG	FADGI	iDigBio	Rec. DROID	NYBG	JSTOR	UPDIG	None	
		Standard										

Figure 10: Standard awareness by institution size

Numbers in bold represent percentages of respondents within each institution size, numbers within parentheses are absolute number of responses. Please note that percentages do not add up since respondents could check more than one standard. Percentages can be interpreted as “the percentage of respondents within each institution size which responded they were aware of a given standard, not excluding the knowledge of other standards”. Standard acronyms: ALA - ALA Guidance: Digitisation: A strategic approach for natural history collections; DPC - Digital Preservation Coalition Handbook; ICEDIG - DISSCO ICEDIG project deliverables 1 through 7; FADGI - Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative; iDigBio Rec. - iDigBio Recommendations for the Acquisition, Processing, and Archiving of Digital Media; DROID - iDigBio Developing Robust Object Image to Data series, 1 through 4; NYBG - NYBG Herbarium Specimen Imaging: Standards and Suggestions; JSTOR - JSTOR Global Plants guidelines; UPDIG - Universal Photographic Digital Imaging Guidelines.

4.3.4 By role

The reported knowledge of standards is very similar across roles. The average knowledge across standards goes from 14% for *Curator* up to 17% for *Informatician*. The variability in knowledge of the different standards is also very similar to them all.

Role within institution	Standard									
	ALA	DPC	ICEDIG	FADGI	iDigBio	Rec.DROID	NYBG	JSTOR	UPDIG	None
Other	15.4 (23)	7.4 (11)	14.8 (22)	7.4 (11)	19.5 (29)	14.1 (21)	26.2 (39)	26.2 (39)	3.4 (5)	45 (67)
Researcher	7.8 (16)	3.9 (8)	8.7 (18)	2.4 (5)	17.5 (36)	9.7 (20)	24.8 (51)	24.8 (51)	3.9 (8)	52.9 (109)
Informatician	8.3 (3)	5.6 (2)	8.3 (3)	13.9 (5)	16.7 (6)	13.9 (5)	13.9 (5)	22.2 (8)		50 (18)
Digitiser	7.4 (4)	5.6 (3)	14.8 (8)	7.4 (4)	13 (7)	16.7 (9)	18.5 (10)	14.8 (8)	1.9 (1)	55.6 (30)
Curator	7 (26)	3.8 (14)	8.4 (31)	2.2 (8)	14.4 (53)	7.9 (29)	17.9 (66)	20.1 (74)	2.2 (8)	56.4 (208)
Collection manager	11.2 (31)	4.7 (13)	6.1 (17)	2.9 (8)	19.1 (53)	10.4 (29)	20.5 (57)	23 (64)	1.4 (4)	55.4 (154)
Administrator	8.9 (9)	5.9 (6)	10.9 (11)	2 (2)	10.9 (11)	7.9 (8)	15.8 (16)	15.8 (16)	1 (1)	61.4 (62)

Figure 11: Standard awareness by role

Numbers in bold represent percentages of respondents within each role, numbers within parentheses are absolute numbers of responses. Please note that percentages do not add up since respondents could check more than one standard. Percentages can be interpreted as “the percentage of respondents within each role which responded they were aware of a given standard, not excluding the knowledge of other standards”. Standard acronyms: ALA - ALA Guidance: Digitisation: A strategic approach for natural history collections; DPC - Digital Preservation Coalition Handbook; ICEDIG - DISSCO ICEDIG project deliverables 1 through 7; FADGI - Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative; iDigBio Rec. - iDigBio Recommendations for the Acquisition, Processing, and Archiving of Digital Media; DROID - iDigBio Developing Robust Object Image to Data series, 1 through 4; NYBG - NYBG Herbarium Specimen Imaging: Standards and Suggestions; JSTOR - JSTOR Global Plants guidelines; UPDIG - Universal Photographic Digital Imaging Guidelines.

4.4 Standards use

4.4.1 Overall

The overall use of standards follows the same distributional pattern as the reported awareness, except for DISSCO ICEDIG which here has a lower value relative to the others. The

number of respondents that assert making use of each standard are much lower than those relating to standard awareness, *i.e.* suggesting that standards are not always being used despite the familiarity with them. The difference between these values and those corresponding to awareness is even higher than it appears since the use of standards could be answered for more than one preparation type while the awareness of them was only answered once.

Figure 12: Standard use

4.4.2 Awareness versus use

The gap between awareness of standards and their actual use is quite large. The standards that have the best relation are *DISSCO ICEDIG*, *iDigBio DROID* and *JSTOR* with 55.5%, 53.9% and 49.4%, respectively. The standards with the worst relations are *ALA*, *iDigBio Recommendations* and *DPC* with 30.5%, 30.8% and 37.5%, respectively. Within the ICEDIG Deliverables and the iDigBio DROID series, there are substantial differences between their different standards. From 4.2% (*ICEDIG Deliverable 3.7*) to 32.1% (*ICEDIG Deliverable 3.6*) for the ICEDIG Deliverables, and from 6.5% (*iDigBio DROID 3*) and 41.8% (*iDigBio DROID 1*) for the iDigBio DROID series.

(a) Standard groups

(b) Standard groups - detail

Figure 13: Standard awareness vs use

4.4.3 By country

JSTOR guidelines is the mostly used standard reported with a total of 33 countries, followed by *NYBG* with 24 and *DISSCO ICEDIG* with 19. *DPC*, *FADGI*, *iDigBio DROID* are the least used with a total of 6, 6, and 6 countries each, respectively.

Figure 14: Standard use by country

4.4.4 By role

The use of standards by role follows a general pattern similar to that of the awareness of standards. However, numbers here are rather lower.

Role within institution	Standard									None
	ALA	DPC	ICEDIG	FADGI	iDigBio Rec	DROID	NYBG	JSTOR	UPDIG	
Other	6 (9)	2 (3)	6 (9)	2.7 (4)	4.7 (7)	6 (9)	11.4 (17)	8.1 (12)	1.3 (2)	38.9 (58)
Researcher	2.4 (5)		3.4 (7)	0.5 (1)	6.3 (13)	4.9 (10)	11.2 (23)	11.7 (24)	1.5 (3)	41.3 (85)
Informatician	2.8 (1)		2.8 (1)	5.6 (2)	8.3 (3)	2.8 (1)	5.6 (2)	13.9 (5)		41.7 (15)
Digitiser	1.9 (1)	1.9 (1)	7.4 (4)	1.9 (1)	7.4 (4)	9.3 (5)	7.4 (4)	13 (7)		37 (20)
Curator	2.2 (8)	0.3 (1)	2.2 (8)	0.8 (3)	5.7 (21)	2.7 (10)	8.7 (32)	11.4 (42)	0.3 (1)	41.5 (153)
Collection manager	4.3 (12)	1.4 (4)	2.2 (6)	1.8 (5)	6.5 (18)	6.5 (18)	11.2 (31)	13.3 (37)	1.4 (4)	41 (114)
Administrator	2 (2)	1 (1)	1 (1)		4 (4)	3 (3)	5.9 (6)	9.9 (10)	1 (1)	40.6 (41)

Figure 15: Standard use by role

Numbers in bold represent percentages of respondents within each role, numbers within parentheses are absolute numbers of responses. Please note that percentages do not add up since respondents could check more than one standard. Percentages can be interpreted as “the percentage of respondents within each role which responded they used a given

standard, not excluding the use of other standards”. Standard acronyms: ALA - ALA Guidance: Digitisation: A strategic approach for natural history collections; DPC - Digital Preservation Coalition Handbook; ICEDIG - DISSCO ICEDIG project deliverables 1 through 7; FADGI - Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative; iDigBio Rec. - iDigBio Recommendations for the Acquisition, Processing, and Archiving of Digital Media; DROID - iDigBio Developing Robust Object Image to Data series, 1 through 4; NYBG - NYBG Herbarium Specimen Imaging: Standards and Suggestions; JSTOR - JSTOR Global Plants guidelines; UPDIG - Universal Photographic Digital Imaging Guidelines.

4.5 Obstacles

4.5.1 Overall

The main obstacles were *Lack of staff time*, *Financial*, and *Lack of equipment* which were reported by a 24.6%, 20.3% and 14%, respectively. Only 2.4% reported having no obstacles to imaging.

Figure 16: Obstacles

4.5.2 By country

The distribution pattern of reported obstacles by country is not remarkably different for different types of obstacles. Some countries do not report some obstacles but this is very contingent on the number of institutions reported by country and the institutions themselves. However, it is worth mentioning that the only countries where there was at least one institution which reported having no obstacle are: Australia, Bahamas, Brazil, Canada, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Portugal, Singapore, Slovakia, South

Africa, Sweden, Switzerland, United States .

Figure 17: Obstacles by country

4.5.3 By institution size

Financial and lack of staff time obstacles show a slight increase towards bigger institutions, while lack of equipment shows the opposite (bigger institutions report less the lack of equipment as an obstacle to imaging). This is also true but to a lesser extend for lack of expertise. Reporting too much preparation as an obstacle also increases with the size of the institution. Being not aware of standards or not being a priority does not follow a distinct pattern across institution sizes. Institutions which report no obstacles increase from small institutions to institutions with sizes sizes between 500k and 1M and then decrease again towards the biggest institutions.

Figure 18: Obstacles by institution size

4.5.4 By preparation type

Lack of staff time is the most reported obstacle across all preparation types, followed by financial obstacles except for ‘Dried - assembled’ and ‘Fossils (2D)’. In general, patterns of reported obstacles are very similar across preparation types.

Figure 19: Obstacles by preparation type

4.5.5 By collection type

Similar to preparation types, lack of staff time is the most reported type of obstacle across collection types, followed by financial obstacles for all collection types except ‘Palaeontology (vertebrates)’. Lack of equipment also stands out for ‘Botany/Algae/Fungi’ and ‘Zoology (Vertebrates)’. For the most reported type, ‘Botany/Algae/Fungi’, aside from lack of staff time and financial obstacles, the other two obstacles most reported are the lack of equipment and not being a priority.

Figure 20: Obstacles by collection type

4.5.6 By collection size

The distribution of collection sizes by reported obstacles are quite similar for any given obstacle. All median collection sizes per obstacle fall within the range of mid-sized collections, i.e. between 14375 and 110000. In terms of percentage of overall reported specimens affected by each type of obstacle, *Lack of staff time* is the most reported with 29.0% of specimens affected, followed by *Financial* with 22.5% and *Too much preparation* with 13.7%. Having *No obstacles* to imaging is associated with only 2.8% of the specimens.

Figure 21: Obstacles by collection size

4.6 Preparation types

4.6.1 By country

Herbarium sheets are reported across all countries answering the survey, in accordance with the collection types above. All ‘Dried and pinned’ types have been reported from American and European institutions plus New Zealand. ‘Liquid preserved’ have been reported from the Americas, Europe, Kenya, Namibia and New Zealand. ‘Microscope slides’ have been reported from the United States and Brazil, and from Denmark, Luxembourg, Switzerland and the United Kingdom in Europe. ‘Dried - assembled’ have been reported from Europe (Luxembourg, Italy and Portugal), America (United States), Asia (Philippines) and Oceania (New Zealand). ‘Dried - not assembled’ have been reported

from American and European Countries plus India, Thailand and New Zealand. Fossils (2D) have been reported only from European countries and the United States. Fossils (3D) have been reported from France, Italy, Luxembourg, the United States and New Zealand. ‘Geological macro-objects’ have only been reported from Norway, Sweden, the United States and New Zealand. Still, other types of preparations have been reported from countries across all continents.

Figure 22: Preparation types by country

4.6.2 By collection type

The percentage of responses for each combination of preparation type and collection type is highest for *Herbarium sheets - Botany / Algae / Fungi* with a 53.2% responses, followed by *Dried and pinned - Zoology (Invertebrates)* with a 5.4% responses, and *Dried - not assembled - Zoology (Vertebrates)* with a 3.3%. The percentage of collection types reported for *Other* preparation types is 9.4% responses. All other collection types for the rest of preparation types account for a 28.7%.

Figure 23: Preparation types by collection type

4.6.3 By collection size

Per preparation type, collections show different distributions of sizes. *Microscope slides* show the smallest range of sizes, from 55 to 100 000 , although based on only 1 answer. On the other hand, *Dried - not assembled* show the largest range, from a collection as small as 50 to a collection as large as 30 000 000, based on 1 answer. Herbarium sheets which are the largest preparation type in number of responses range from only 1 to 7.8 million, based on 330 answers. It is worth noting the very low number of specimens reported from some collections, *e.g.* less than 5, which might be an error in the data entered.

Figure 24: Preparation types by collection size

4.7 Image content

4.7.1 Elements included

Overall *Label(s)*, *Scale bar*, and *Catalogue number* are the elements most included in images, followed by *Colour chart* and *1D Barcode (e.g., Code 39)*. *2D Barcode (e.g., QR Code)* is the least included element in images.

Figure 25: Image content - Elements included

By preparation type The previous pattern of *Label(s)*, *Scale bar*, and *Catalogue number* being the three most included elements holds true for each preparation type except for *Geological macro-objects* and *Herbarium sheets*. *2D Barcode (e.g. QR Code)* are not used by *Liquid preserved*, *Fossils (3D)*, *Fossils (2D)*, and *Dried - assembled*.

Figure 26: Image content - Elements included per preparation type

4.7.2 Image kinds

Overall For the vast majority of respondents, a *Whole specimen overview* image is included, followed by *Individual parts*, and *Label only*. *Multispectral* images have been reported by only a few respondents.

Figure 27: Image content - Image kinds

By preparation type *Whole specimen overview* and *Individual parts* are also the images most taken for each preparation type, except of *Dried and pinned*. *Multispectral*

images appear to be taken only for *Herbarium sheets* and *Microscope slides*.

Figure 28: Image content - Image kinds by preparation type

4.8 Image format

4.8.1 Format

Overall *JPEG* is the most widely used image format, followed by *TIFF*, and *RAW*. *JP2 (JPEG 2000)*, *3D*, and *Tiled*, in this order, are the least used image formats.

Figure 29: Image content - Image format

By preparation type The same pattern as before appears for each preparation type. *Stacked depth images* play a relative major role in *Fossils (2D)*, and *Tiled* images are noticeable as the fourth used format in *Microscope slides*.

Figure 30: Image content - Image format by preparation type

4.9 Image quality

4.9.1 Colour (bit) depth

Overall Most respondents report taking images at 24-bit depth, followed by 8- and 16-bit depth.

Figure 31: Image quality - Colour depth

By preparation type Imaging at 24-bit depth predominate in all preparation types, except for *Liquid preserved* and *Fossils (3D)*, for which 16-bit depth predominate, and for *Fossils (2D)* for which it is equal to 8-bit depth.

Figure 32: Image quality - Colour depth by preparation type

4.9.2 Colour space

Overall 78% of respondents report using the *RGB* colour space, while only a 17% use the *sRGB* and 5% use the *CMYK*.

Figure 33: Image quality - Colour space

By preparation type *RGB* predominates across all preparation types and *sRGB* is second, except of *Other*. The *CMYK* colour space is only mentioned for *Dried and pinned*, *Herbarium Sheets*, and *Other* preparation types.

Figure 34: Image quality - Colour space by preparation type

4.9.3 Colour calibration

Overall 33% of respondents report performing colour calibration and 67% do not.

Figure 35: Image quality - Image calibration

By preparation type In all preparation types predominate images which are not colour calibrated. *Other*, *Dried and pinned*, and *Herbarium sheets* are the preparation types with higher percentages of colour-calibrated images.

Figure 36: Image quality - Image calibration by preparation type

4.9.4 Image sharpening

Overall 29% of respondents report sharpening images and 71% report not.

Figure 37: Image quality - Image sharpening

By preparation type In all preparation types prevail the non application of sharpening techniques to images, except for *Fossils (3D)*, for which the percentage of respondents who report sharpening the images is equal to those that do not.

Figure 38: Image quality - Image sharpening by preparation type

4.9.5 Colour correction

Overall 27% of respondents report applying colour correction to images and 73% do not.

Figure 39: Image quality - Colour correction

By preparation type In all preparation types prevail the non application of colour correction techniques to images. This predominance is minimal for *Fossils (2D)*, *Fossils (3D)*, and *Geological macro-objects*.

Figure 40: Image quality - Colour correction by preparation type

4.9.6 Image cropping

Overall 41% of respondents report cropping images and 59% do not.

Figure 41: Image quality - Image cropping

By preparation type Cropping of images is predominant for *Fossils (2D)*, *Fossils (3D)*, *Microscope slides*, and *Other* preparation types. For the rest of preparation types non-cropping is the norm. For *Dried - assembled* an equal number of respondents report cropping and non-cropping images.

Figure 42: Image quality - Image cropping by preparation type

4.10 Image metadata

4.10.1 Standards

Overall The vast majority of respondents (77%) report using *No standard* for image metadata, 9% use *Audubon Core*, and 14% use other standards.

Figure 43: Image metadata - Standards

By preparation type For all preparation types the use of *No standard* predominate over *Audubon Core* and *Other* standards. *Audubon Core* is not mentioned for *Dried - assembled* and *Geological macro-objects*.

Figure 44: Image metadata - Standards by preparation type

4.10.2 Storage

Overall *EXIF* is used by 69 respondents to store image metadata, while 32 use *XMP*. None of the respondents reported using any other type of storage as mentioned in the survey question; *i.e.* *IPTC*, *Separate from image file, in a database*, *Separate from the image file, in a spreadsheet or csv*, *Other*. Also, none reported that metadata were *Not stored*.

Figure 45: Image metadata - Storage

By preparation type *EXIF* predominates across all preparation types, except for *Dried - assembled* for which it is equally used as *XMP*.

Figure 46: Image metadata - Storage by preparation type

4.10.3 Profiles

4.10.3.1 HERBARIUM SHEETS

General info

Standard used	N
None	174
Other	37
UPDIG Guidelines	5
JSTOR Guidelines	76
NYBG Standards	65
iDigBio DROID 2	1
iDigBio DROID 1	24
iDigBio Recommendations	20
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.7	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.6	16
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.1	3
FADGI guidelines	3
Digital Preservation Coalition	6
ALA Guidance	17

Collection type	N
Botany / Algae / Fungi	338
Zoology (Invertebrates)	3
Zoology (Vertebrates)	1
Microorganisms	4
Other	4

Obstacle	N
Financial	201
Lack of staff time	213
Lack of equipment	142
Lack of expertise	80
Too much preparation	59
Not a priority	83
Not aware of standards	65
No obstacles	25
Other	26

Image type	N
Whole specimen overview	282
Individual parts	20
Trait detail	11
Label only	16
3D	4
Multispectral	3
Other	18

Image quality

Element included	N
1D Barcode (e.g. Code 39)	158
2D Barcode (e.g. QR code)	30
Catalogue number	193
Colour chart	196
Institutional name/logo	231
Label(s)	234
Scale bar	216
Other	19

Format	N
JPEG	235
JP2 (JPEG 2000)	12
TIFF	121
RAW	83
3D	2
Stacked depth images	5
Tiled	5
Other	38

Colour space	N
RGB	165
sRGB	29
CMYK	10
Other	47

Colour bit depth	N
8 bit	37
12 bit	12
16 bit	29
24 bit	87
48 bit	20
Other	50

Is calibrated	N
Yes	84
No	155

Is corrected	N
Yes	60
No	182

Is sharpened	N
Yes	68
No	172

Is cropped	N
Yes	88
No	155

Metadata standard	N		Metadata storage	N	
Audubon Core	21				
No standard	197				

Additional comments given for each preparation type question. In order to anonymize comments where necessary, actual names of institutions have been changed to X.

Collections: Angiosperms — Fungi specimens — Photography on glass, carpological objects, hand-written books — vascular plants

Standards used: custom process with photographic camera to achieve final images similar to the obtained with JSTOR Global Plants guidelines — Digital Transitions guidelines for sale for cultural heritage <https://heritage-digitaltransitions.com/product-category/digitization-guides/> — e-recolnat — Elements of JStor Global Plants, but we will be following that standard in the near future (within a month, I hope) — eRecolNat project - <https://www.recolnat.org/fr/> — For types specimens, we use the Jstor Global Plants guidelines, and for other specimens, we use the SpeciesLink guidelines. — GBIF — <http://www.nsii.org.cn/2017/home-en.php> — <http://www.snsb.info/SNSBInfoOpenWiki/attach/Attachments/JSTOR-Plants-Handbook.pdf> This is as close as I can find to the manual we use which was provided by X in 2009 to go with our herbscan. It is titled 'Specimen Scanning Manual' Edited by Della Lindsay authors Marion Crick, Anna Saltmarsh and Sarah Phillipss. — <https://biokic.github.io/symbiota-docs/> — <https://www.gbif.org/project/2as3Q2nNvRQhMc30JzAQ6e/digitization-of-specimens-at-the-university-of-the-philippines-los-banos-museum-of-natural-history> — <https://www.tropicos.org> — I don't know what all of that stuff means, we digitized according to the dictates of the Consortium of Pacific Northwest Herbaria — I don't know which protocol was followed. The collection was imaged at the University of Colorado Herbarium in Boulder, Colorado, USA — INCT-Virtual Herbarium Guiderlines — JABOT (mainly), Species Link — local collection of plates and photographs — Local protocol — Macroalgal Herbarium Consortium - <http://macroalgae.unh.edu/> — Methods developed internally. — Mexican National Herbarium Guidelines of the National Autonomous University of Mexico, <http://www.ib.unam.mx/botanica/herbario/colecciones/> — Only occasional scanning, upon request — REFLOA - Brazilian Plants: Historic Rescue and Virtual Herbarium for Knowledge and Conservation of the Brazilian Flora — Reflora Digitization Manual <http://dspace.jbrj.gov.br/jspui/handle/doc/103> — Rio de Janeiro Botanical Garden guidelines — Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew — Scanning — SERNEC which I think uses iDigBio? — Specific Herbarium MA protocol — Standards that are specified in various NSF funded, collaborative TCN projects; elements of above listed resources that are adapted to HUH's specific infrastructure — Still researching standards in preparation for imaging — swiss collection management handbook, https://swisscollnet.scnat.ch/en/uuid/i/c911ed14-87ec-5d12-afb0-a34438f414a9-Handbook_on_natural_history_collections_management — the digitization of type specimens was hosted by Botanic Garden Meise — We generally follow practices recommended by

GBIF national node in Portugal — while ICEDIG Deliverable 3.6 was not specifically used during digitization process, this fit very closely the approach used corresponds very closely.

Obstacles: Collections on military installations so need permission — Coordinating with University of the Philippines Los Baños Museum of Natural History Staff. — External factors associated with operating in a heritage building — I used guidelines from Ron Jones, Eastern KY University — image storage/backup — Inadequate man-power and equipment — IT support — Lack of staff — lack of staff , only honorary collaborators — Lack of staff (1 only, doing all) — Long term cost of image storage — many specimens need restoration prior to digitization — Need to obtain new camera lens to switch from flatbed-scanner to camera/copystand — Nonexistent infrastructure — not applicable — Not prioritized by staff. — Online portal not being managed or accepting specimen images — Our imaging is principally for providing fast access to images, and especially for label data. — Started this imaging before these (most of them) standards was in place — Taxonomic group not an institutional priority — technical competences, staff — We had considered using a Herbscan but the cost of transport was much too high for an acquisition in French Guiana — We have not yet started imaging of specimens but have obtained all equipment to do so — We now have very high quality camera, stand, etc. but we are running into program compatibility issues, which will be sorted but this takes more time due to constraints of support staff and my time. — we use a mix of different guidelines — we use volunteers for most of the digitization work and this can sometimes lead to a higher error rate than if staff were to do it

Image elements: Barcode only for types as catalog number is the collection number — Botanical drawings and watercolours of the species in the living collection — EWU Accession Number — Golden Thread object level target — hand held photos and cropped used for BOLD about 1/3 of collection is genetically barcoded. — N/A — none — None — none of these — Not applicable — Specimen and 'fragments' — this is a wish list response — We do not image. — We use both an datamatrix code with catalog number and a qgr code with an uuid — We were recently able to acquire the necessary colour chart — Will use standards used by University of the Philippines Los Baños Museum of Natural History

Image types: including detached parts of plants in the small envelope attached to herbarium sheet — N/A — New identifications — ninguna — none — None — Not applicable — Occasionally 1) in situ and/or 2) microscopy. — Occasional additional images are made, if the label is very long and has been folded, or if there are separate drawings by collector that describe the specimen, or if they are critical pieces in the fragments envelope. — Parts of specimen inside pockets that have any of them — sample fragments such as pieces of leaves, flowers and/or fruits — Some priority taxa have trait images also — sometimes details (flower or fruit ; fungi, mosses if required) — We do not image. — We haven't taken any pictures yet. — Will use imaging standards used by University of the Philippines Los Baños Museum of Natural History

Image formats: - — Also stored as DNG — CR2 — dng — DNG — DNG (digital negative) — Don't know, can't remember — I don't know — I don't know. — I oversee the operation but I do not

know the answer to this question. — in e-recolnat — JP80 — N/A — nef — NEF — none — None — Not applicable — Not sure — pdf — pdf but they can be translate in JPEG — RAW converted to DNG — SID — unknown at this early stage — We do not image. — We're working with a larger institution to take images; I don't know their protocols — Will use formats used by University of the Philippines Los Baños Museum of Natural History

Image format info: - — As we transition into a digital asset management system we are transferring images traditionally saved as DNG files into Tiff. A shareable JPG copy is also kept. — Currently RAW and JPEG; RAWs are proprietry, plan to save RAW to TIFF. Images from Nikon SMZ25, e.g. of seeds and fruits are stacked images usually TIFF. — HD — Herbarium number — Meta deta of labels — None — normal size — Not applicable — nothing was filled because we have not done any imaging yet, although we wanted... — Ordinary herbarium sheets are kept both as RAW and JPEG Nomenclatural Type sheets are kept as TIFF — Our types specimens of vascular plants were digitized on others herbarium. — RAW (CR2) Images are retained until after images have been quality-checked and converted into JPEGs and DNGs. — RAW = Moss — RAW file format is nef, — Raw format for most AR specimens is CR2 — Raw or Tiff depending on camera — Stacked images only for a small part of the imaged specimens. JPEGs used for display. — The images taken so far are sporadic, no standards were adopted, only trying to get the best image we can with the (private) photo equipment available. — The scanned herbarium sheet photos are kept as TIFF & the photographed specimens are kept as RAW. Both are published online as jpg. For stack photographed types, all RAW's are kept, for non-types only the stack as TIFF in a PSD. — TIFF is our raw format that is only kept for type specimens. JP2 lossless compression and reversible as kept format for all the specimens and as web access format via IIP server. — We capture the images in RAW, but upload in JPEG to the servers. — We currently save RAW files under the proprietary format, eg .mos. — We save LZW compressed TIFFs in the archive and work with 90

Image quality: A pipeline is performed on TIF files in batch to verify and check file names, repeated images, resolution, orientation, tiff quality and format. The quality of the jp2 files is also controlled: valid jp2, correct format, integrity and correct reversibility and metadata conversion — As above, our images are principally for informatics, not for taxonomic purposes. The entire herbarium is "portable" in this format. — Cropping is only done to the extent of the herbarium sheet edge. — Due to the lack of personnel and the equipment the images were taken at a different institution and I am unaware of most of the parameters. Additionally, I just took over the role of curator and I'm still in the process of becoming familiar with everything. — Epsom standard RGB-Gamma 1.8 — For our herbarium sheets (scanned for the Global Plants) we had to stitch together two images; one of most of the sheet (normaly with the plant and part of the label) and one smaller image with (often) the bottom part of the sheet (rest of label and specimen id), due to too long sheets for the scanners. — HD — herbarium specimens are almost but not quite 2d-objects. Therefore we use a many-point-average focus to make sure most of the specimen is within the depth of focus. — I think it's a 40MP photo (4608x3456x24bpp). — If a researcher wants a higher quality image, we would make those if the request came in. Right now our focus is to get everything into the X Herbaria. — Images are kept as they are taken (as the camera sees it), i.e. without any modifications and then cropped — Images cropped and rotated — Lens distortion

correction — Lichen/bryophyte images are label only and cropped to include just the packet, vascular plants are entire sheets. — N/A — n/a because we have not yet started imaging our specimens, so lack these specifics — Nil — No questions about lighting! Our current set up uses professional flash units with diffuser boxes, but this is never as even or good as it should be. We are moving to a light box with balanced LEDs and the lighting is far superior in colour temperature and evenness. — None — Not applicable — Not clearer — nothing was filled because we have not done any imaging yet, although we wanted... — Our digital cameras automatically do corrections for various optical aberrations, but we still do white-point correction post-capture. — Quality not good enough due to lack of recommended imaging equipment and tools — Single portion images are generated and thereafter a composition with photo merge is done. — The images taken so far are sporadic, no standards were adopted, only trying to get the best image we can with the (private) photo equipment available. — We do not image. — We sent our collection to the Texas Oklahoma Regional Consortium for imaging. — We're working with a larger institution to take images; I don't know their protocols — White balance and exposure are carried out using the Golden Thread colour chart. — Whitebalance, sharpening and light uniformity reset if any change to setup — You do not use the scanner / herbscan system (we cropped at that time it took too much time to get an image - around 6 minutes), but a camera (no cropping, instant image !)

Image colour depth: - — ? — 12 Mb — 24 bit for tiff images — 32 — 32 bit — As imaging will only start coming September we have so far not decided on resolution, colour depth and colour space — can't answer — desconozco — don't know — Don't know. — I don't know. — I don't know. I use a Canon EOS Mark II Digital SLR, 21 megapixel, Canon Ef 50 mm macro — I fill this survey from home, not able to check it, but we are using the flat bed Epson Scanner provided within Global Plants Initiative; we have also camera PhaseOne, 150 Mgp — n/a because we have not yet started imaging our specimens, so lack these specifics — Na/ — none — None — Not applicable — not certain — not known — not quite sure — Not quite sure. — not sure — Not sure — Not sure, this is handled by our IT personnel — The images have been taken in another institution, I am not sure about this. — unknown — unsure — Unsure — We do not image. — We're working with a larger institution to take images; I don't know their protocols — Will use color depth standards used by University of the Philippines Los Baños Museum of Natural History

Image colour space: - — ? — ? I do not know... sorry — Adobe RGB (1998) — AdobeRGB — As imaging will only start coming September we have so far not decided on resolution, colour depth and colour space — Colour card next to herbarium sheet — Do not recall (sorry) — Don't know. — eciRGB v2 — I do not know this — I don't know — I don't know. — I think that it's CMYK? We use a Cannon Camera. — N/A — n/a because we have not yet started imaging our specimens, so lack these specifics — none — None — Not applicable — not known — Not quite sure. — Not specified — not sure — Not sure — Not sure, this is handled by our IT personnel — RGB Adobe 198 — RGB for tiff images — Specifically RGB Adobe 1998 — sRGB before 2012, RGB after 2012. — unknown — Unsure — We do not image. — We're working with a larger institution to take images; I don't know their protocols — Will use color space standards used by University of the Philippines Los Baños Museum of Natural History

Image colour calibration: x ? — As imaging will only start coming September we have so far not decided on resolution, colour depth and colour space — Automatic — Before 2017, yes. — camera settings worked out before imaging takes place — Colour card is used next to specimens and camera is calibrated once — colour scale is included in image but not used in calibrating color actively — Currently no, but plan to do this within a month — Don't remember. — I don't know — I don't know. — I dont know — n/a because we have not yet started imaging our specimens, so lack these specifics — none — Not applicable — Not for all images — Not for all setups, due to staff time and financial limitations — not sure — Not sure — Occasionally I double check settings and compare to original — Standards are not uniform. — the camera is supposed to be calibrated at every job session — This is handled by our IT personnel — Unknown — unsure — Unsure — We do not image. — We have a calibration software, but it's old and doesn't work as well as when set up with a photo professional. — We're working with a larger institution to take images; I don't know their protocols — White balance — white balance is adjusted at beginning of session

Image colour sharpening: ? — As imaging will only start coming September we have so far not decided on resolution, colour depth and colour space — Automatic — camera settings worked out before imaging takes place — Can't remember. — Currently no, but we will trial slight sharpening with the 100s — For bryophytes yes, not for larger vascular plants. Images don't seem to need it? — I don't know. — If needed — if required — n/a because we have not yet started imaging our specimens, so lack these specifics — none — Not applicable — not know as images are made by external service provider — not sure — Not sure — scanner not, camera yes — sometimes — unknown — Unknown — unsure — Unsure — We do not image. — We have not yet had to deal with unusually thick specimens. — We're working with a larger institution to take images; I don't know their protocols — Yes, Archive DNGs saved with nondestructive Lightroom edits

Image colour correction: ? — As imaging will only start coming September we have so far not decided on resolution, colour depth and colour space — As part of setting up the scanner after a long time without use. — Automatic — Before 2017, yes. — camera settings worked out before imaging takes place — Hi — I don't know. — If needed — n/a because we have not yet started imaging our specimens, so lack these specifics — none — Not applicable — not sure — Not sure — Not sure, this is handled by our IT personnel — unknown — Unknown — unsure — Unsure — We do not image. — We're working with a larger institution to take images; I don't know their protocols — white balance — white balance only. — Yes, Archive DNGs saved with nondestructive Lightroom edits

Image cropping: ? — Archive DNGs are not cropped. JPEGs in CMS are cropped with digital ruler applied. — As imaging will only start coming September we have so far not decided on resolution, colour depth and colour space — Cropped and not cropped — I don't know. — image includes only sheet plus surrounding scale and colour bars to avoid having to crop images. this is possible because specimens are standard in dimensions. — Imaging of packeted collections is cropped — n/a because we have not yet started imaging our specimens, so lack these specifics — none — Not any more. — Not applicable — Not sure — Only for details — only small embeded images of the content of enveloppes — Sometimes — sometimes if necessary — sometimes, if necessary — the edges of the images are cropped

— They are cropped to show the different part plants with the cropped images saved as separate files.
— To the edge of the herbarium sheet only. Yes, if we are making additional detail images. — unknown
— Unknown — Unsure — usually not — Usually not, but sometimes necessary — Very slightly but
whole sheet is included — We do not image. — We're working with a larger institution to take images;
I don't know their protocols

Image metadata standard: ? — As imaging will only start coming September we have so far not
decided on resolution, colour depth and colour space — BRAHMS — csv — Darwin core — Darwin
Core — Darwin cores — darwincore — Darwincore — DarwinCore — Data for each specimen are being
entered into Merlin database — Edinburgh Code — going to use darwincore — I do not know. — I
don't know. — in-house developed method — It will be integrated with the acquisition register — Jacq
— JSTOR Global Plants guidelines — Macroalgal Herbarium Consortium — maybe Audubon Core,
not sure. Darwin-Core — n/an/a because we have not yet started imaging our specimens, so lack these
specifics — nil — none — Not applicable — not sure — Not sure — Penelope and excel — Symbiota
DwC A format — unknown — Unknown — unsure — Unsure — we do but it was developed in-house
— We do not image. — We will review this. — We're working with a larger institution to take images;
I don't know their protocols — Will use metadata standards used by University of the Philippines Los
Baños Museum of Natural History

Image storage: None

4.10.3.2 LIQUID PRESERVED

General info

Standard used	N
None	23
Other	1
UPDIG Guidelines	1
NYBG Standards	1
iDigBio DROID 3	2
iDigBio Recommendations	4
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.4	1
ALA Guidance	2

Collection type	N
Botany / Algae / Fungi	3
Zoology (Invertebrates)	15
Zoology (Vertebrates)	15
Microorganisms	1
Other	1

Obstacle	N
Financial	18
Lack of staff time	24
Lack of equipment	15
Lack of expertise	11
Too much preparation	7
Not a priority	10
Not aware of standards	11
No obstacles	2
Other	2

Image type	N
Whole specimen overview	27
Individual parts	10
Trait detail	1
Label only	7
3D	1

Image quality

Element included	N
1D Barcode (e.g. Code 39)	1
Catalogue number	19
Colour chart	5
Institutional name/logo	6
Label(s)	17
Scale bar	17
Other	4

Format	N
JPEG	23
TIFF	9
RAW	8
3D	1
Stacked depth images	2
Other	1

Colour space	N
RGB	14
sRGB	4
Other	6

Colour bit depth	N
8 bit	4
16 bit	9
24 bit	1
Other	9

Is calibrated	N
Yes	6
No	19

Is corrected	N
Yes	5
No	16

Is sharpened	N
Yes	6
No	18

Is cropped	N
Yes	9
No	12

Metadata standard	N	Metadata storage	N
Audubon Core	1	EXIF	2
No standard	24	XMP	1

Additional comments given for each preparation type question. In order to anonymize comments where necessary, actual names of institutions have been changed to X.

Collections: Fishes

Standards used: In-house specimen photography guidelines

Obstacles: Protocols we follow are developed for fresh specimen photography onboard research vessel. Standards are prescribed to fit existing guides that NIWA prepares for various clients. We currently have no specific protocol for already preserved specimens due to lack of funding to address this. — We are imaging specific views for species identification (diagnostic features), which are species/taxon specific views. Image size is dictated by database requirements.

Image elements: Not applicable — or unique temp number if not yet cataloged — Specimen with label, if possible or just specimen — These do not apply, as the images now existing were taken in the field when the specimens were alive

Image types: None

Image formats: DICOM

Image format info: Not known - photography section take the images — the type of image is dependent on the equipment used, which is determined by the size of the object/specimen

Image quality: image quality varies widely depending on size of object, if it is wet or dry, and what equipment is used (microscope camera, automontage imaging system, type of camera (Nikon, Cannon, Sony) and other variables — Photos were black and white

Image colour depth: ? — no idea — Not known - photography section take the images — not recorded — Not sure — unknown — unsure — variable

Image colour space: ? — Not known - photography section take the images — not recorded — Not sure — unsure — variable

Image colour calibration: x Not known - photography section take the images — sometimes

Image colour sharpening: Not known - photography section take the images — sometimes — sometimes, if needed

Image colour correction: If needed — Not known - photography section take the images — sometimes — Sometimes — sometimes, if needed

Image cropping: If needed — Not known - photography section take the images — sometimes — sometimes, if needed

Image metadata standard: NIWA standards set — Not known - photography section take the images

Image storage: None

4.10.3.3 MICROSCOPE SLIDES

General info

Standard used	N
None	7
Other	2
UPDIG Guidelines	1
iDigBio Recommendations	2
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.2	1
FADGI guidelines	1
Digital Preservation Coalition	1
ALA Guidance	1

Collection type	N
Botany / Algae / Fungi	4
Zoology (Invertebrates)	6
Paleontology (Invertebrates)	1
Paleontology (Vertebrates)	1
Geology (including meteorites)	1
Microorganisms	1
Other	2

Obstacle	N
Financial	7
Lack of staff time	9
Lack of equipment	5
Lack of expertise	6
Too much preparation	4
Not a priority	4
Not aware of standards	6
No obstacles	2
Other	1

Image type	N
Whole specimen overview	8
Individual parts	3
Trait detail	1
Label only	3
Multispectral	1
Other	2

Image quality

Element included	N
1D Barcode (e.g. Code 39)	1
2D Barcode (e.g. QR code)	1
Catalogue number	8
Institutional name/logo	2
Label(s)	7
Scale bar	5
Other	1

Format	N
JPEG	7
JP2 (JPEG 2000)	1
TIFF	7
RAW	3
Stacked depth images	1
Tiled	2

Colour space	N
RGB	2
sRGB	1
Other	2

Colour bit depth	N
8 bit	1
24 bit	4
Other	2

Is calibrated	N
No	5
Yes	1

Is corrected	N
Yes	1
No	6

Is sharpened	N
Yes	3
No	5

Is cropped	N
Yes	8
No	1

Metadata standard	N		Metadata storage	N	
Audubon Core	2				
No standard	8				

Additional comments given for each preparation type question. In order to anonymize comments where necessary, actual names of institutions have been changed to *X*.

Collections: Comparative Archaeological Slides — Soil Thin Section Slides

Standards used: Internal metadata standard (no link) — no specific protocol was followed

Obstacles: Pictures taken long before standards were developed.

Image elements: none

Image types: Multiple light sources (plane polarized, cross polarized, reflected) — Non-subject edges are cropped.

Image formats: None

Image format info: None

Image quality: images cropped to better fit slide format — Usually cropped to specimen boundary

Image colour depth: 24-bit color for microscope images, 8-bit images for SEM — unknown

Image colour space: unknown

Image colour calibration: x unknown

Image colour sharpening: unknown

Image colour correction: unknown

Image cropping: None

Image metadata standard: Internal metadata standard

Image storage: None

4.10.3.4 DRIED AND PINNED

General info

Standard used	N
None	25
Other	4
UPDIG Guidelines	2
NYBG Standards	1
iDigBio DROID 4	1
iDigBio DROID 2	4
iDigBio Recommendations	4
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.7	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.6	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.5	3
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.4	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.3	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.2	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.1	2
FADGI guidelines	2
Digital Preservation Coalition	2
ALA Guidance	3

Collection type	N
Botany / Algae / Fungi	1
Zoology (Invertebrates)	34
Zoology (Vertebrates)	2
Other	3

Obstacle	N
Financial	24
Lack of staff time	29
Lack of equipment	13
Lack of expertise	9
Too much preparation	12
Not a priority	13
Not aware of standards	12
No obstacles	1
Other	4

Image type	N
Whole specimen overview	32
Individual parts	4
Trait detail	5
Label only	10
3D	1
Other	3

Image quality

Element included	N
1D Barcode (e.g. Code 39)	2
2D Barcode (e.g. QR code)	8
Catalogue number	25
Colour chart	8
Institutional name/logo	14
Label(s)	20
Scale bar	22
Other	3

Format	N
JPEG	28
JP2 (JPEG 2000)	2
TIFF	19
RAW	8
3D	1
Stacked depth images	15
Other	2

Colour space	N
RGB	20
sRGB	3
CMYK	1
Other	6

Colour bit depth	N
8 bit	6
16 bit	5
24 bit	9
48 bit	2
Other	8

Is calibrated	N
Yes	12
No	18

Is corrected	N
Yes	7
No	21

Is sharpened	N
Yes	6
No	23

Is cropped	N
Yes	12
No	14

Metadata standard	N		Metadata storage	N	
Audubon Core	3				
No standard	28				

Additional comments given for each preparation type question. In order to anonymize comments where necessary, actual names of institutions have been changed to X.

Collections: entomology — Entomology — Zoology (insects)

Standards used: A combination of different standards based on specific project protocols — no idea — no specific protocol used — own modifications depending on the specimen

Obstacles: Existing standards need to be refined — Only used for digitisation requests for research (not cataloguing purposes). And for type material. — potential harm of specimens — reservation of collection curation staff

Image elements: Data matrix, but not currently being imaged — Digitally added scale bar

Image types: Stacked images — whole unit tray images of dorsal view

Image formats: (stacked images for some but not all material imaged depending on subject and depth-of-field constraints) — dng

Image format info: Most of the insects we are digitizing are built through stacking. — Uploads are usually jpg, original images jp2, tif used for publication; some images just phone through ocular — Use internal standards, which cover humanities and natural history

Image quality: La pagina web (<https://www.agrosavia.co/ctni/ctc>) exige unas medidas para poder subirlas. Tenemos siempre la de alta calidad, pero las de la pagina pierden, por los requerimientos precisos de la web. — Not currently imaging since resources are limited — Quality depends on lighting, often a lot of reflections, so lighting is adjusted (ringlight Y/N, filtering paper). Number of stacking images depends on object. White balance is adjusted by eye. ZEISS stacking microscope — These are areas we had not even considered, there is much to think about. — We usually save different size, resolution and format for each image.

Image colour depth: 14 — don't know — I don't know — not sure — unknown — Varies

Image colour space: don't know — Golden Thread Lab — I don't know — not standardized, not aware which has been used so far — unknown

Image colour calibration: x white balance

Image colour sharpening: Sometimes as required, extra step though.

Image colour correction: depending on the need; usually not — white balance

Image cropping: depending on the need; usually not — depends on the image — Sometimes — usually no, but varying

Image metadata standard: darwincore — Initially no; Now adopting Audubon Core going forward

Image storage: None

4.10.3.5 DRIED AND ASSEMBLED

General info

Standard used	N
None	7
Other	1
UPDIG Guidelines	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.3	1
Digital Preservation Coalition	1

Collection type	N
Zoology (Invertebrates)	2
Zoology (Vertebrates)	11
Paleontology (Invertebrates)	1
Paleontology (Vertebrates)	2
Paleontology (botany / algae / fungi)	1
Geology (including meteorites)	2
Other	1

Obstacle	N
Financial	4
Lack of staff time	10
Lack of equipment	7
Lack of expertise	5
Too much preparation	2
Not a priority	3
Not aware of standards	7
Other	1

Image type	N
Whole specimen overview	10
Individual parts	4
Trait detail	1
Label only	2
Other	1

Image quality

Element included	N
Catalogue number	5
Colour chart	1
Institutional name/logo	1
Label(s)	5
Scale bar	5
Other	2

Format	N
JPEG	8
TIFF	7
RAW	4
Other	2

Colour space	N
RGB	7
sRGB	2
Other	1

Colour bit depth	N
8 bit	2
16 bit	2
24 bit	3
48 bit	1
Other	1

Is calibrated	N
Yes	1
No	10

Is corrected	N
Yes	2
No	9

Is sharpened	N
Yes	4
No	7

Is cropped	N
Yes	5
No	5

Metadata standard	N		Metadata storage	N	
No standard	10				
			XMP	3	

Additional comments given for each preparation type question. In order to anonymize comments where necessary, actual names of institutions have been changed to *X*.

Collections: Bird Study Skins

Standards used: no specific protocol used

Obstacles: Guidelines do not apply to the images being created. Guidelines are limiting.

Image elements: currently nothing — Sometimes color chart and scale bar

Image types: Images of art work created from specimens

Image formats: 35 mm negative — DNG

Image format info: None

Image quality: strongly varying quality due to no specific protocol applied.

Image colour depth: No idea.

Image colour space: No idea.

Image colour calibration: x None

Image colour sharpening: None

Image colour correction: None

Image cropping: usually no

Image metadata standard: Arctos media image information

Image storage: None

4.10.3.6 DRIED NOT ASSEMBLED

General info

Standard used	N
None	30
Other	8
UPDIG Guidelines	1
JSTOR Guidelines	2
NYBG Standards	3
iDigBio DROID 4	3
iDigBio DROID 2	1
iDigBio DROID 1	2
iDigBio Recommendations	7
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.7	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.6	2
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.5	2
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.4	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.3	2
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.2	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.1	2
FADGI guidelines	6
Digital Preservation Coalition	3
ALA Guidance	4

Collection type	N
Botany / Algae / Fungi	20
Zoology (Invertebrates)	14
Zoology (Vertebrates)	21
Paleontology (Invertebrates)	4
Paleontology (Vertebrates)	3
Paleontology (botany / algae / fungi)	2
Geology (including meteorites)	2
Other	2

Obstacle	N
Financial	22
Lack of staff time	42
Lack of equipment	16
Lack of expertise	11
Too much preparation	10
Not a priority	10
Not aware of standards	9
No obstacles	4
Other	8

Image type	N
Whole specimen overview	32
Individual parts	17
Trait detail	6
Label only	13
3D	5
Other	5

Image quality

Element included	N
1D Barcode (e.g. Code 39)	10
2D Barcode (e.g. QR code)	6
Catalogue number	25
Colour chart	19
Institutional name/logo	21
Label(s)	27
Scale bar	31
Other	5

Format	N
JPEG	33
JP2 (JPEG 2000)	2
TIFF	22
RAW	13
3D	3
Stacked depth images	7
Tiled	1
Other	7

Colour space	N
RGB	17
sRGB	11
Other	6

Colour bit depth	N
8 bit	4
12 bit	3
16 bit	5
24 bit	10
Other	10

Is calibrated	N
Yes	10
No	21

Is corrected	N
Yes	8
No	22

Is sharpened	N
Yes	7
No	24

Is cropped	N
Yes	10
No	20

Metadata standard	N	Metadata storage	N
Audubon Core	6	EXIF	13
No standard	25	XMP	3

Additional comments given for each preparation type question. In order to anonymize comments where necessary, actual names of institutions have been changed to X.

Collections: objects >10cm — Zooarchaeology (Vertebrates)

Standards used: custom protocol with photographic camera to achieve similar images with JS-TOR Global Plants guidelines — [https://ams.wildapricot.org/resources/Documents/Standard views for imaging mollusk shells for web 2019.pdf](https://ams.wildapricot.org/resources/Documents/Standard%20views%20for%20imaging%20mollusk%20shells%20for%20web%202019.pdf) — institutional standards based on LOC preservation guidelines — Metamorfoze standard <https://www.metamorfoze.nl/digitalisering> — Paul Callomon, 2019, Standard views for imaging mollusk shells, [https://ams.wildapricot.org/resources/Documents/Standard views for imaging mollusk shells for web 2019.pdf](https://ams.wildapricot.org/resources/Documents/Standard%20views%20for%20imaging%20mollusk%20shells%20for%20web%202019.pdf) — Specific Herbarium MA protocol — Standard Views for Imaging Mollusk Shells by Paul Callomon — TENN GLOBAL imaging protocol: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/17Tm-kCtNAXtIbIajgA2Ca54q3EQNsZK/view>

Obstacles: lack of storage for digital images — Limited uniformity in what users want and need — no software to store images — objects are too diverse; mounting as well — published protocols/guidelines too rigidly tied to specific equipment — Specimens are arranged synoptically by element — The type of digitization we are creating is not something in those guidelines — There is no ability to host images on site - no software

Image elements: 3D models have additional information in the specimen page — field photos — I have no images — Taxonomy — unknown

Image types: A "lot view" showing all specimens in a lot may also be taken. Detail images sometimes taken if there are any unusual or hard to see features. — I have no images — Imaging kinds depend on objects. Labels are always photographed. Micro- and macrographs are taken of selected specimens only — Multiple views of one specimen (this should be one of the options above...) — Various views, SEM, Light Microscope

Image formats: dng — DNG — DNG files sometimes also kept — I have no images — PNG and DNG — RAW is point of attention

Image format info: PNG and DNG are the preferred formats, usually we also store a jpeg for the collections to work with

Image quality: 3D imaging (10 of 3,000) performed previously, standards unknown — Color temperature is measured and adjusted every two weeks. — Our digital archives go back to 2003, so we have a lot of variation — Use Photoshop to consolidate images into one plate — White balance and exposure carried out using X-Rite colour chart

Image colour depth: 14 bit — 32 bit — Don't know — I have no images — Not sure — unknown — unsure — variable — various

Image colour space: Depending on the photo camera features — no idea what this is — Not sure — RGB I think — unknown

Image colour calibration: x I have no images — initial calibration not monitored — Not sure — variably — Work in progress

Image colour sharpening: depends on image type — I have no images — Not sure — sometimes — variably

Image colour correction: I have no images — Not sure — Only extremely rare, using white calibration — sometimes

Image cropping: I have no images — Not sure — Not usually, but occasionally — Sometimes — sometimes (rarely) — sometimes (usually not)

Image metadata standard: Darwin Core - associatedMedia — Diversity Workbench db internal image standard — I have no images — institutional Standard

Image storage: None

4.10.3.7 FOSSILS 2D

General info

Standard used	N
None	4
Other	3
UPDIG Guidelines	1
iDigBio DROID 4	1
iDigBio Recommendations	1
ICEDIG Deliverable 3.1	1
FADGI guidelines	1
Digital Preservation Coalition	1
ALA Guidance	2

Collection type	N
Botany / Algae / Fungi	1
Paleontology (Invertebrates)	9
Paleontology (Vertebrates)	6
Paleontology (botany / algae / fungi)	6
Geology (including meteorites)	2
Microorganisms	1

Obstacle	N
Financial	3
Lack of staff time	5
Too much preparation	3
Not a priority	4
Not aware of standards	3
Other	2

Image type	N
Whole specimen overview	10
Individual parts	6
Label only	4
3D	1

Image quality

Element included	N
1D Barcode (e.g. Code 39)	1
Catalogue number	7
Institutional name/logo	5
Label(s)	6
Scale bar	8
Other	2

Format	N
JPEG	8
TIFF	7
RAW	1
3D	1
Stacked depth images	2

Colour space	N
RGB	7
sRGB	1
Other	1

Colour bit depth	N
8 bit	3
24 bit	3
48 bit	2
Other	1

Is calibrated	N
Yes	1
No	8

Is corrected	N
Yes	4
No	5

Is sharpened	N
Yes	3
No	5

Is cropped	N
Yes	6
No	1

Metadata standard	N		Metadata storage	N	
Audubon Core	2				
No standard	8				

Additional comments given for each preparation type question. In order to anonymize comments where necessary, actual names of institutions have been changed to X.

Collections: None

Standards used: Digitization workflows for paleontology collections (<https://palaeo-electronica.org/content/2016/1569-digitization-workflows>) — Made our own written standards inhouse tailored to our needs. — no specific guideline has been used

Obstacles: Lack of digital space to store images — Our tailored protocols work fine but the listed ones are all too wordy and general - there are good points but for our purpose we need to the point instructions with photograph manual how to proceed step by step so that visitors / or new staff easily can understand the steps.

Image elements: Name of taxa, place, date — scale bar only included sporadically, or when using digital microscope

Image types: None

Image formats: None

Image format info: None

Image quality: none — quality improved over the years, but legacy images with low resolution and quality

Image colour depth: ?

Image colour space: ?

Image colour calibration: x Only for those selected for publication

Image colour sharpening: Several photos are taken for each item, the fuzzy ones are discarded and the rest are kept. Those that are used for publication in journals are improved by sharpening but the ones kept in the database are not. That would take enormous resources and completely unrealistic. — sometimes

Image colour correction: se comments above for image sharpening.

Image cropping: on occasion yes — plants: no; invertebrates: yes — se comments above for image sharpening.

Image metadata standard: None

Image storage: None

4.10.3.8 FOSSILS 3D

General info

Standard used	N
None	7
Other	2
iDigBio DROID 4	1
iDigBio Recommendations	1
FADGI guidelines	1
Digital Preservation Coalition	2

Collection type	N
Paleontology (Invertebrates)	5
Paleontology (Vertebrates)	9
Paleontology (botany / algae / fungi)	1

Obstacle	N
Financial	4
Lack of staff time	9
Lack of equipment	4
Lack of expertise	3
Too much preparation	2
Not a priority	2
Not aware of standards	4
Other	2

Image type	N
Whole specimen overview	10
Individual parts	8
Trait detail	1
Label only	2
3D	4
Other	4

Image quality

Element included	N
1D Barcode (e.g. Code 39)	1
Catalogue number	7
Colour chart	2
Institutional name/logo	3
Label(s)	4
Scale bar	10

Format	N
JPEG	9
TIFF	8
RAW	4
3D	3
Stacked depth images	3
Tiled	1
Other	2

Colour space	N
RGB	7
sRGB	3

Colour bit depth	N
8 bit	1
16 bit	5
24 bit	3

Is calibrated	N
Yes	1
No	7

Is corrected	N
Yes	3
No	4

Is sharpened	N
Yes	4
No	4

Is cropped	N
Yes	5
No	4

Metadata standard	N	Metadata storage	N
Audubon Core	2	EXIF	4
No standard	9	XMP	3

Additional comments given for each preparation type question. In order to anonymize comments where necessary, actual names of institutions have been changed to X.

Collections: None

Standards used: no specific protocol used — Paul Callomon, 2019, Standard views for imaging mollusk shells, [https://ams.wildapricot.org/resources/Documents/Standard views for imaging mollusk shells for web 2019.pdf](https://ams.wildapricot.org/resources/Documents/Standard%20views%20for%20imaging%20mollusk%20shells%20for%20web%202019.pdf). Also EPICC TCN's Standard Views of Marine Invertebrates for Photography, available under "Protocols & Workflows": https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Documenting_Fossil_Marine_Invertebrate_Communities_of_the_Eastern_US_Faunal_Responses_to_Environmental_Change_over_the_last_66_million_years#Protocols_.26_Workflows

Obstacles: Negative feedback from aggregators that only want "pretty" things imaged — We have our own standard

Image elements: None

Image types: 32 images for 360 degree view — A "lot view" showing all specimens in a lot may also be taken. Trail detail images sometimes taken if there are any unusual or hard to see features. — drawings, diagrams — high-resolution CT

Image formats: DNG — DNG sometimes also kept

Image format info: Obj and stl files — Some TIFF images have also been retained, but JPEG has been more common due to file size storage requirements.

Image quality: We modify images at little as possible.

Image colour depth: None

Image colour space: None

Image colour calibration: x It depends — sometimes — unknown

Image colour sharpening: sometimes — Sometimes — unknown

Image colour correction: It depends — sometimes — Sometimes — unknown

Image cropping: It depends — Sometimes

Image metadata standard: None

Image storage: None

4.10.3.9 GEOLOGICAL MACROOBJECTS

General info

Standard used	N
None	3
Other	1
FADGI guidelines	1
Digital Preservation Coalition	1

Collection type	N
Paleontology (Vertebrates)	1
Geology (including meteorites)	5

Obstacle	N
Lack of staff time	3
Lack of expertise	1
Not a priority	1
Not aware of standards	3
Other	1

Image type	N
Whole specimen overview	5
Individual parts	3

Image quality

Element included	N
2D Barcode (e.g. QR code)	1
Catalogue number	3
Colour chart	1
Label(s)	1
Scale bar	3

Format	N
JPEG	5
TIFF	4
RAW	2
Stacked depth images	1
Other	1

Colour space	N
RGB	3
sRGB	2

Colour bit depth	N
16 bit	2
24 bit	3

Is calibrated	N
No	5

Is corrected	N
Yes	2
No	3

Is sharpened	N
No	5

Is cropped	N
Yes	1
No	3

Metadata standard	N		Metadata storage	N	
No standard	4				
			XMP	2	

Additional comments given for each preparation type question. In order to anonymize comments where necessary, actual names of institutions have been changed to *X*.

Collections: None

Standards used: Internal metadata standard (no link)

Obstacles: Plenty of expertise exists but it's not evenly distributed. There's rarely time to find and fix images created by staff members who do not know or follow standards.

Image elements: None

Image types: None

Image formats: DNG

Image format info: None

Image quality: None

Image colour depth: None

Image colour space: None

Image colour calibration: x None

Image colour sharpening: None

Image colour correction: None

Image cropping: Sometimes

Image metadata standard: Internal metadata standard

Image storage: None

Acknowledgements

We wish to express our gratitude to all people who have committed some of their time to answering this survey and making it possible. Sharif Islam has provided crucial assistance in making the survey possible with the DiSSCo (<https://www.dissco.eu>) and MOBILISE CA17106 resources.

References

- [1] R Core Team. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. Vienna, Austria, 2023. URL: <https://www.R-project.org/>.

5 Appendix 1 - List of institutions

A total of 702 respondents answered the survey, of which 640 (91.2%) stated their institution (this question was optional). Following is the alphabetically ordered list of these reported institutions. Names appear as reported.

Academy of Natural Sciences of Drexel University — Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia — Acopian Center for Ornithology — ACOR Herbarium, National University of Córdoba — AGRARIA Department, Mediterranean University of Reggio Calabria — Agricultural & Horticultural research Station, Ullal, Mangalore — Agrotechnological Academy at the V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University — Alexandru Ioan Cuza University from Iasi — Allan Herbarium, Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research — Ambika Prasad Research Foundation — American Museum of Natural History — American Samoa Community College — Angelo State Natural History Collections — ANHC, APCR, HEND, HOSP, HXC, OUF, STAR, UAM, UARK, UCAC — ANSP — Appalachian State University — Arboretum/Pinetum Lucus Augusti — Arizona State Museum — Arizona State University — Arizona State University NEON Biorepository — ASU Insect Collection — Auburn University at Montgomery — Auckland War Memorial Museum — Augustana College (IL) — Bailey-Matthews National Shell Museum — Ball State University — Baltimore Woods Nature Center, Inc — Banasthali Vidyapith — Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan — Belarusian State University — BHCBC Herbarium - Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais — Biodiversity Institute, University of Kansas — Biological Museum (Botany LD), Lund university — Biological museum Oskarshamn, herbarium OHN — Bishop Abraham Memorial College, Thuruthicad — Bishop Museum — Bishop Museum Herbarium Pacificum — Blatter Herbarium, St. Xaviers College, Mumbai, India — Bohart Museum of Entomology — Bolus Herbarium, University of Cape Town — Botanical Garden "D. Brandza", University of Bucharest — Botanical Garden of Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice — Botanical garden of Talence — Botanical garden of the H.S. Scovoroda Kharkiv national pedagogical university — Botanical Garden of Vlnius University — Botanical Research Institute of Texas — Botanical Survey of India — Botanical survey of India, Central Regional Centre, Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh — Botanical survey of India, Central Regional Centre, Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh, — Botanische Staatssammlung München — Botanischer Garten und Botanisches Museum Berlin — Bressanone Pharmacy Museum — Brigham Young University — Bristol Museums, Galleries & Archives — British Institute at Ankara — British Institute at Ankara (BIAA) — Buffalo Museum of Science — Bureau of Land Management District Office — Bureau of Land Management- Salmon Field Office — C.M. Rick Tomato Genetics Resource Center — Cadereyta Regional Botanical Garden (Council of Science and Technology of the State of Queretaro) — Calcutta University Herbarium — California Academy of Sciences — California Academy of Sciences - Anthropology — California Academy of Sciences - BOTANY — California Academy of Sciences, Invertebrate Zoology — California Polytechnic State University, Robert F. Hoover Herbarium (OBI) — California State University Channel Islands — California State University Northridge Botanic Garden — California State University San Bernardino Herbarium — California State University, Long Beach — California State University, Northridge — Calvin University — Canadian Museum of Nature — Canterbury Museum — Carnegie Museum — Carnegie Museum of Natural History — Carnegie Museum of Natural History, Section of Mollusks — Cartagena Botanical Garden — casabio.org — Center of Excellence in Fungal Research, Mae Fah Luang University — Central Siberian Botanical Garden SB RAS — Centre National Floristique — Centre Suisse de Recherches Scientifiques en Côte

d'Ivoire — Centro Studi Erbario Tropicale - FT (Dip.to Biologia, Università degli studi di Firenze) — Chadron State College — Charles University — Chateau Perouse Botanical Gardens — Chrysler Herbarium — CICYTTP-CONICET-Prov.ER-UADER — City of Boulder, Colorado — Claude Garton Herbarium - Lakehead University — Cleveland Museum of Natural History — Colección de Escarabajos Coprófagos de Colombia — Colección Teriológica, Universidad de Antioquia — Colecciones Biológicas Universidad CES — colonial williamsburg arboretum — Colorado Mesa University — Colorado State University, Center for the Environmental Management of Military Lands — Columbia-Greene Community College — Connecticut College Arboretum — Conservatoire et Jardin botaniques de Genève — Cornell College — Cornell University Museum of Vertebrates — Corporación Colombiana de Investigación Agropecuaria (Agrosavia). Colección Taxonómica Nacional de Insectos "Luis María Murillo" (<https://www.agrosavia.co/ctni>) — Cox Arboretum and Gardens Canton, Georgia — CSIC — CSIR-NBRI — CSIRO — Davis & Elkins College — De La Salle University Herbarium — Denver Botanic Gardens — Denver Museum of Nature & Science — Department of Botany, Government College University, Lahore Pakistan — Department of Pharmacognosy, Obafemi Awolowo University — Department of Plant and Fungal Diversity and Resources, Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences — Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, University of Jos, Jos, Nigeria — Dept of Biodiversity, Conservation & Attractions. — Desert Botanical Garden — Dian Fossey Gorilla Fund International Herbarium — Discovery Collections, National Oceanography Centre — Division of Invertebrate Zoology, Burke Museum, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington, USA — Dublin City University — Eastern New Mexico University Miles Mineral Museum — Eastern Washington University — Ecosystems Research and Development Bureau — Ecovida — Edwards Aquifer Research and Data Center - Aquifer Biodiversity Collection — Embrapa Clima Temperado — Emirates Center for Wildlife Propagation — ENAG - Herbario Universidad Nacional Agraria (UNA) — Entomology, Biological Museum, Lund University — ERDB-DENR — Estonian Museum of Natural History — Estonian University of Life Sciences — ETHZ Entomological Collection — Evanston Township High School Arboretum — Far Eastern University — Fern and Nature Society of the Philippines — Field Museum — Field Museum of Natural History — Finger Lakes Community College — Finnish Museum of Natural History — Fiocruz — Fondazione Museo Civico di Rovereto — Forest Products Research and Development Institute - Department of Science and Technology — Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria — Fort Hays State University Sternberg Museum of Natural History — Fort Lewis College — Fresno city College — Fundação Casa da Cultura de Marabá — Fundación Jardín Botánico "Guillermo Piñeres" (Cartagena Botanical Garden) — Fungarium CMMF, University of Montréal — Fungarium of United Herbaria Zurich (Z+ZT) — G.T. Velasquez Phycological Herbarium and The Marine Science Institute, University of the Philippines Diliman — George T. Jones Herbarium, Oberlin College — Georgia Southwestern State University — Giardini Botanici Hanbury /Hanbury Botanic Gardens — Glenville State University — Gonabad medical university — Goulandris Natural History Museum — Government Post Graduate College Bannu — Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve — Granite Mountains Desert Research Center (GMDRC) — Grenfell Campus, Memorial University of Newfoundland — Grinnell College — Grootfontein Agricultural Development Institute — HARRAN University Herbarium — Harvard University — Harvard University Herbaria — Hattori Botanical Laboratory — Hawaii Department of Agriculture — HDJF / UFVJM — Hebei Normal University — Herbário "Guido Pabst" GFJP — Herbário Mongoyós - Universidade Federal da Bahia

(IMS/CAT/UFBA) — Herbaria Basel, University of Basel — Herbario Amazónico ECUAMZ de la Universidad Estatal Amazónica — Herbario Catatumbo-Sarare (HECASA), universidad de Pamplona — Herbario de la Universidad de Sevilla — Herbario LEB Jaime Andrés Rodríguez — Herbario Nacional Forestal "Martín Cárdenas" BOLV — Herbario Nor Peruano (HNOP) — Herbario régional de Guayan — Herbario Trelew de la FCNyCS - Universidad Nacional de la Patagonia San Juan Bosco — Herbario y Jardín Botánico, Universidad Nacional de San Luis, Argentina — Herbarium — Herbarium and Botanic Garde, Benemerita Universidad Autonoma de Puebl;a — Herbarium BDWR — Herbarium der Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule (ZT) — Herbarium Escuela Superior Politécnica del Chimborazo CHEP — Herbarium GB — Herbarium GB, Gothenburg — Herbarium Gießen — Herbarium Hazara University (HUP), Mansehra Pakistan — Herbarium Instituto de la Patagonia - Universidad de Magallanes — Herbarium KL — herbarium LJU — Herbarium LOU. Centro de Investigación Forestal de Lourizán-AGACAL — Herbarium Malangensis — Herbarium NHG Nuremberg — Herbarium of Aarhus University — Herbarium of Geo. B. Hinton — Herbarium of Kochi University — Herbarium of Museu Nacional (acronym "R"). Rio de Janeiro, Brazil — Herbarium of new Caledonia (NOU) — Herbarium of the Dresden University of Technology (DR) — Herbarium of the Northwestern Luzon, Philippines (HNUL) — Herbarium of the University of Coimbra — Herbarium of Universidade do Algarve (ALGU) — Herbarium of VN Karazin Kharkiv National University (CWU) — Herbarium SPF - Universidade de São Paulo — Herbarium UB — Herbarium UME — Herbarium Universitatis Camerinensis — Herbarium Universitatis Ticinensis (PAV) - University of Pavia — Herbarium university of Dar es salaam — Herbarium UPNA — Herbarium, Biodiversity Research Museum, Academia Sinica, Taipei — Herbarium, Botany Department, Trinity College Dublin — Herbarium, Queen Sirikit Botanic Garden, The Botanical Garden Organization, Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment — Herbarium, University of Reading — Herbert Art Gallery & Museum — Herbier du Québec (QUE), Gouvernement du Québec — Herbier Marie-Victorin — Herbier Marie-Victorin (MT) — Hereford Museum Service — Hermanus Botanical Society — Highstead — HNU Herbarium of VNU University of Science, Hanoi — Hodgdon Herbarium at the University of New Hampshire — Hong Kong Herbarium — Houston Arboretum and Nature Center — Howard Payne University — HPBR- URI — HSMC (Hortus Siccus McMurtrianus) — Hungarian Natural History Museum — Hunter Region Botanic Gardens — ICAR-Central Arid Zone Research Institute Regional Research Station — ICAR-Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi — Icesi Herbarium — Illinois Natural History Survey Insect Collection — illinois Natural History Survey Mollusk Collection — Illinois State Univ — Indiana State Museum — Indiana University — Institut Botànic de Barcelona (Museu de Ciències Naturals de Barcelona) — Institut de Recherche pour le Développement — Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences — Institute of Biology Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics Ss. Cyril and Methodius University Arhimedova Str. 3 1000 Skopje, Republic of North Macedonia — Institute of Dendrology, Polish Academy of Sciences — Institute of Forest Ecology SAS, Plant Pathology Herbarium (NR), Nitra, Slovakia — Institute of General and Experimental Biology, Siberian Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences — Instituto Colombiano de Medicina Tropical — Instituto de Biología, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México — Instituto de Ecología A.C. — Instituto de Investigaciones Botánicas y Zoológicas, Universidad Autónoma de Santo Domingo — Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas y Costeras (IIMyC.CONICET-UNMdP/FCEyN) — Instituto de Pesquisa Ambiental (former Instituto de Botânica) — Instituto Federal de Educação Ciência e Tecnologia Farroupilha — Instituto Federal

do Pará, Campus Abaetetuba — Instituto Nacional de Investigacion en Salud Publica — Instituto National de Pesquisas da Amazonia (INPA) — Instituto Patagonico para el Estudio de los Ecosistemas Continentales - Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (IPEEC - CONICET) — Instituto Tecnológico de Tlajomulco, Jalisco — Ioulia & Alexandros N. Diomidis Botanical Garden — Iowa Lakeside Laboratory — ISAAA — Ivan Franko National University of Lviv — J.J. Triana Herbarium — Jardín Botánico de Acapulco — Jardi Botanic de Soller — Jardim Botánico de Brasília — Jardin botanique de Montréal — Jihoceske muzeum v Ceskych Budejovicich — João de Carvalho e Vasconcellos Herbarium (LISI), from ISA / University of Lisbon — Jordan Royal Botanic Garden — Jose Vera Santos Memorial Herbarium (PUH) — Kirklees Museums and Galleries — Knox College Herbarium — Komarov Botanical Institute of the Russian Academy of sciences — Korea National Arboretum — KTU Herbarium University of Silesia in Katowice, Poland — L’Institut Agro Rennes Angers — La Brea Tar Pits Museum — Laurie L. Consaul Herbarium (UWO) — Leon Levy Native Plant Preserve — Lewis-Clark State College — Lobachevsky State University of Nizhny Novgorod — Lomonosov Moscow State University — Loyola University of Chicago — Luhansk Taras Shevchenko National University — Luther College — M.M.Gryshko National Botanical Garden of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine — MACB Herbarium — MAF Herbarium. Herbario de la Facultad de Farmacia de la Universidad Complutense de Madrid — Maidstone Museums — MAPR herbarium; University of Puerto Rico, Mayaguez — Maria Mitchell Association — Marine Vertebrate Collection, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, UCSD — Marshall University Herbarium — Maryland Department of Natural Resources (TAWES) — Masaryk University, Faculty of Science, herbarium BRNU — MDQ herbarium — Medicinal Plants — Meise Botanic Garden — Michigan State University — Middlesbrough Museums — Milwaukee Public Museum — Mining museum Příbram, botanical department — Ministère de la recherche et de l’enseignement supérieur — Missouri Botanical Garden — Missouri State Parks — Montana Entomology Collection — Montana State University Northern — Montpellier University — Multiplant International medicinal conservation — Musée de Tahiti et des îles - Te Fare Manaha — Musée et Jardins botaniques cantonaux — Muséum national d’histoire naturelle — Museo Nacional de Costa Rica — Museo Argentino de Ciencias Naturales - Bernardino Rivadavia — Museo civico di Storia Naturale di Sondrio — Museo de Ciencias Naturales José Celestino Mutis Universidad de Pamplona — Museo de Historia Natural de El Salvador — Museo de La Salle-Universidad de La Salle — Museo Erbario Sapienza University of Rome — Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales — Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (CSIC) — Museo Universitario de La Universidad de Antioquia — Museu de História Natural do Funchal — Museu de História Natural e da Ciência da Universidade do Porto (MHNC-UP) — Museu Nacional de História Natural e da Ciência — Museu Nacional de História Natural e da Ciência da Universidade de Lisboa — Museu Nacional de História Natural e da Ciência, universidade de Lisboa — Museu Nacional do Rio de Janeiro — Museum des sciences naturelles d’Angers — Museum für Naturkunde Berlin — Museum fuer Naturkunde Berlin — Museum of NATural History St.Gallen — Museum of Riverside (formerly Riverside Metropolitan Museum) — Museum of Southwestern Biology, Fishes — Museum of Vertebrate Zoology — MVFA Herbarium — Mycological collection (lichens and fungi), Natural History Museum and Botanical Garden, University of Tartu — Mycological collection, Natural History Museum and Botanical Garden, University of Tartu — Mzaman Aquatic Herbarium — N.C.W. Beadle Herbarium (NE) — National Botanic Garden of Wales — National Collection of Vascular Plants (DAO) — National Gallery of Albania — National Herbarium of

NSW — National Herbarium of Tanzania - NHT — National Herbarium of Ukraine (KW) — National Museum of Namibia — National Museum of Natural History — National Museum of Natural History, Luxembourg — National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution — National Museum of Natural History, Sofia, BAS — National Museum Prague — National Museums of Kenya — National Museums Scotland — National Tropical Botanical Garden — Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County, Malacology Department — Natural History Collections of Bavaria — Natural History Museum — Natural History Museum Basel — Natural History Museum of Denmark — Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County — Natural History Museum of Utah — Natural history museum, Oslo — Natural Resources Canada, Canadian Forest Service, Northern Forestry Centre — Natural Sciences Museum of Barcelona — Naturalis — Naturalis Biodiversity Center — Naturmuseum Winterthur — Natuurmuseum Brabant — Navajo Natural Heritage Program — NBU herbarium, University of North — Near East Herbarium — New England Botanical Club — New Mexico State University — New York Botanical Garden — New York State Museum — NIWA — no associated with an institution — North Bohemian Museum in Liberec (Severofčeské muzeum v Liberci - original name) — North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences — North Dakota State University Herbarium — North-West University — Northern Arctic Federal University named after M.V. Lomonosov — Northern Illinois University — Northern State University — Northern Territory Herbarium — OAL — Ocean Genome Legacy, Northeastern University — Ohio University — Oklahoma State University — Olds College — Oman Natural History Museum — Omsk State Pedagogical University — Oregon State University — Oregon State University Ichthyology Collection — ORO — Otari Native Botanic Garden — PADA — Paleontological Research Institution — Patanjali Research Institute — Peabody Museum of Natural History, Yale University — Penang Botanic Gardens — Penn State University — Philippine Herbarium of Cultivated Plants, Institute of Crop Science — Phycological Lab Herbarium, University Of Messina — Picturae — Plant gateway — Plant Gene Resources of Canada — PMSP Herbarium, Municipal Secretary for Green Areas and Environment, São Paulo City Hall — Polar Rock Repository, The Ohio State University — Pontificia Universidad Javeriana — Portland State University — Portsmouth Museums — PSUB Herbarium at Okavango Research Institute, University of Botswana — Punjabi University Patiala — Qarshi Botanical Garden , Qarshi industries pvt ltd. Pakistan — R.L. McGregor Herbarium, Biodiversity Institute, University of Kansas — RBGV — RBINS — Real Jardín Botánico de Madrid CSIC — Reed College — Reserva Natural Vale — REU Herbarium — RJB-CSIC, Madrid — RMCA — Rocky Mountain Biological Laboratory - RMBL — Rotherham Museums, Arts and Heritage — Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh — Royal Botanic Garden Madrid- CSIC — Royal Botanic Gardens Kew — Royal Botanic Gardens Sydney — Royal Botanic Gardens Victoria — Royal Botanical Gardens (Ontario) — Royal British Columbia Museum — Rutgers University — São Paulo State University, at Rio Claro — Saile Echegaray Provincial Herbarium belonging to the National University of San Juan — SANT herbarium — Science Museum of Minnesota — Scion (New Zealand Forest Research Institute) — Senckenberg Research Institute and Natural History Museum — Shandong Drug and Food Vocational college — Sheffield Museums Trust — Shirley C. Tucker Herbarium — Singapore Herbarium, Singapore Botanic Gardens, National Parks Board — SMA - Sistema Museale di Ateneo - Università di Bologna — Smithsonian Institution — Smithsonian Institution - Bird Collection — Smithsonian Institution - National Museum of Natural History - Department of Mineral Sciences — Sociedad Botánica y Zoológica de Sinaloa, I.A.P. — Sonoma State University, part of the California State University system — SORO

herbarium (UFSCar) — Sorsogon State University — South African National Biodiversity Institute — Southeast Missouri State University — Southeastern Louisiana University — Southwestern Adventist University — SP Herbarium — Spanish National Museum of Natural Sciences — SRP at Boise State University — St John's College Cambridge — State Herbarium of South Australia — State Museum of Natural History of the NAS of Ukraine — Stroud District (Cowle) Museum Service — Sultan Qaboos University — SUNY Brockport — Swedish Museum of Natural History — Swedish Museum of Natural History, Geosciences — Tadulako University — Tallinn botanic garden — Tarleton State University Herbarium — Tasmanian Herbarium — Tasmanian Seed Conservation Centre — Te Mara Rakaunui o Aotearoa - National Arboretum of NZ — Te Papa Tongarewa National Museum of New Zealand — Tebiwa Herbarium — Tel Aviv University Botanic Garden — Texas A&M University — Texas A&M University Biodiversity Research and Teaching Collections (mammals) — Texas State University — Texas State University, Edwards Aquifer research and Data Center, Aquifer Biodiversity Collection — Texas Vertebrate Paleontology Collections — TFC Herbarium — The Ark Botanical Garden & Restaurant — The Charleston Museum — The Dawes Arboretum — The Dorothy Clive Garde — The Gandhigram Rural Institute (Deemed to be University) GUD — The Herbarium, Swedish Museum of Natural History, Stockholm — The Museum of Wimbledon — The Museum System, Natural History Museum-Botanical Collections, University of Florence — The National Botanic Gardens of Ireland — The National Botanical Garden of Turkey — The National Herbarium of Suriname (BBS) — The State Dendrological Park 'Olexandri' NAS of Ukraine — The Steinhardt Museum of Natural History Tel Aviv University — The Tasmanian Arboretum Inc. — The University of Arkansas Museum — The University of Texas at Austin — The University of Texas at Austin, Entomology Collection — The University of the West Indies — Toyama Science Museum — Transilvania University of Brasov, Dep. Silviculture — TRN Nicolaus Copernicus University Herbarium — U. Of Lethbridge — U.S. Food & Drug Administration - FDA @ Irvine (California) — UFRN Herbarium — Uman National University of Horticulture — Umeå University — UNB IH — Unidad Multidisciplinaria de Docencia e Investigación, Campus Sisal, Facultad de Ciencias, UNAM — Unitec Institute of Technology — United Herbaria — United States National Arboretum, USDA-ARS — Universalmuseum Joanneum, Herbarium GJO — Universidad de Antioquia — Universidad de Colima — Universidad de Panama — Universidad de San Carlos de Guatemala — Universidad del Azuay — Universidad del Valle — Universidad del Valle, Facultad de Salud, Departamento de Microbiología — Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México — Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México - Instituto de Biología — Universidad Nacional de Chilecito — UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LA AMAZONÍA PERUANA — Universidad Tecnica Particular de Loja — Universidade de Évora — Universidade de Caxias do Sul — Universidade do Vale do Taquari - Univates — Universidade Federal da Paraíba — Universidade Federal de Juiz de Fora — Universidade Federal de Mato Grosso (Setor de Entomologia da Coleção Zoológica - CEMT) — Universidade Federal de Mato Grosso do Sul, Campus do Pantanal — Universidade Federal de Pernambuco — Universidade Federal do Oeste do Pará — Universidade Federal do Recôncavo da Bahia — Universidade Federal Rural do Rio de Janeiro - Department of Botany - Herbarium RBR — Universidade Regional de Blumenau — Universidade estadual de campinas — université Claude Bernard Lyon1 — Université de Lille — Université Laval - Herbarium Louis-Marie — Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB), the herbarium — Universitas Indonesia — Universitat de Girona — Universiti Malaysia Terengganu — Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin — University of Évora - Herbarium — University of Alaska Museum — University of

Alaska Southeast — University of Almería — University of Antananarivo — University of Arizona, Laboratory of Tree-Ring Research — university of Aveiro — University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir — University of Balochistan — University of California Museum of Paleontology — University of California, Riverside Herbarium — University of California, Santa Cruz — University of Camerino — University of Central Oklahoma — University of Chitral — University of Colombo — University of Delaware — University of Florida Herbarium — University of Guam — University of Hohenheim — University of Hohenheim, Stuttgart — University of Houston Coastal Center — University of Illinois (ILL) and Illinois Natural History Survey (ILLS) — University of Johannesburg — University of Kansas — University of Kansas, Invertebrate Paleontology — University of Kentucky — University of Khartoum — University of KwaZulu-Natal — University of Michigan Herbarium (MICH) — University of Michigan Museum of Zoology — University of Minnesota — University of Molise — University of Nevada, Reno — University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria — University of North Dakota — University of Parakou — University of Pretoria, Schweickerdt Herbarium — University of Puerto Rico Mayagüez Campus — University of Salzburg — University of Saskatchewan — University of Sevilla — University of Tennessee Knoxville — University of Texas at Austin, Billie L. Turner Plant Resources Center — University of the Philippines Los Banos -Museum of Natural History — University of Torino - Earth Science Department — University of Toronto — University of Trieste — University of Turku - Botanic Garden — University of Utah — University of Victoria Zooarchaeology Lab — University of Vienna - Herbarium WU — University of Vienna, Herbarium WU — University of Waikato Herbarium — University of Warsaw — University of Wisconsin-Madison Zoological Museum — University of Wyoming — University of Wyoming Museum of Vertebrates — University of Zagreb Faculty of Science Herbarium Croaticum — University Toulouse III — UPLB Museum of Natural History — Uppsala University — US National Fungus Collections/USDA ARS — USDA Forest Service Forest Products Laboratory Center for Wood Anatomy Research — USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service — Utah Department of Agriculture and Food — UTCEC Herbarium/URAI — UWPG - Richard Staniforth Herbarium at The University of Winnipeg — University of Wisconsin Zoological Museum — Virginia Institute of Marine Science — Virginia Museum of Natural History — VIVA College Virar, Palghar District, Maharashtra, India — Volgograd Regional Botanical Garden — Warren Wilson College — Washington State University Dept. of Plant Pathology - Shaw Mycological Herbarium — West Virginia Natural Heritage Program — West Virginia University — West Virginia Wesleyan College — Western Australian Herbarium — Wisconsin Insect Research Collection, at the University of Wisconsin-Madison — Witte Museum — Zamorin's Guruvayurappan College — Zimbabwe Parks and Wildlife Management Authority — Zoological collections, Natural History Museum and Botanical Garden, University of Tartu

6 Appendix 2 - Comments

Following is a list of all comments made by respondents. In order to anonymize comments where necessary, actual names of institutions have been changed to *X*.

- Keep up the good work, its very important. once again i realize how amateuristic we still are despite significant progress! Time to research standards etc. is really the bottleneck.... I realize also I should probably have encouraged my technician more to research standards and propose improvements....
- Herbarium digitalisation is very important. Nevertheless, small herbaria can afford to do so. It would be helpful to join efforts and at least for each region (depending on the country scale) come up with program to join efforts. In each region, one institution could house the digitalisation program, being equipped trained and financed to the digitalisations, and the other region herbaria can join the program and send their specimens to be digitalised, with the same protocol, the same standards and being this data all together in a common platform.
- Would be very interested in learning more about community practices and needs regarding the storage and management of image files and metadata. Also interested in learning more about any standards for 3D imaging (e.g., photogrammetry) and best practices for archiving 3D models.
- I found it difficult to understand how to fill the survey. there should be more options to choose multiple collection/taxa/group/preparation type. and not multiple pages (which is confusing , and may result in poor coverage of survey)
- we need a lot of support from other institutions.
- no imaging was done yet on my institution (*X*) due to lack of funds/equipment/staff, although we wish to do it...
- As imaging will only start coming September and the process has not been prepared in detail most questions in thisquestionnaire have been left open
- I'd love to digitise our collection and could use student volunteers to help but I have no affordable platform to store the large number of large files in the long term.
- I found it hard to answer because while we photograph objects in the collections we do not use a protocol and many images are basic record shots by curators or higher standard ones by a volunteer photographer.
- much of our herbarium collection needs restoration before digitization; our staff (only 1 technician) prioritises databasing and curation of new specimens; therefore, for the moment, digitization is delayed.
- We are very interested in receiving training to perform digitization correctly
- We are at the beginning of imaging specimens in our collection. So far the effort is directed towards databasing specimen-related data.

- It would be great to have a community in Latin America to share experiences from Northamerica and Europe. With extremely diverse biota and few taxonomists, digitization efforts could help us increase our biodiversity knowledge.
- Protocols to low resolution images are best established, nevertheless these low resolution pictures are only to manage collections (avoid handling)
- We are specialized in a few families as Convolvulaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Cyperaceae, Malvaceae, Polygonaceae
- Recién nos estamos iniciando en la practica de compartir imágenes.
- Mexico's botanical gardens, in general, do not have systematic procedures for digitizing images of their living specimens or those kept in other types of collections.
- We are working to develop an image management system, adopting Audubone Core as the meta-data standard for managing specimen images and others, related with the specimens management system.
- In 1990 digitisation of the *X* Herbarium began using a standard database. In 1996 the HERBAR program proposed by the Association of Ibero-Macaronesian Herbarians AHIM was adopted. http://www.ahim.org/html/ahim_marcos.htm . Later, the *X* Herbarium became integrated into the ELYSIA application. All data is currently integrated into the international platform for information on Biodiversity GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility), <https://www.gbif.es/>
- Thank you for the opportunity to participate in the survey. Hopefully in the near future we will have more chances to conduct research at a higher level and with better equipment.
- Our herbarium is the largest in the county established 1965 but we do suffer sufficient funds to operate for some duties especially if there is no project based on herbarium as it is treated as Teaching herbarium type attached to the Botany Department of the University of *X*
- In general, try to document photos of the plant species in the garden, not of all the individual plants.
- We are in the process of coordinating with *X* University.
- If we had staff and time, we would take herbarium samples of aal the species in our living collection. We have some pictures of the species of our plants but it's not complete. The pictures are here and there but we have had attempts to collect these in one place.
- I've answered the survey as best I can, but I don't think it's really aimed at our sort of 'collection', such as it is.
- We began imaging in 2009, or earlier so much hasn't changed, including equipment. The metadata isn't saved separately, so this should probably be considered. Most specimens in the collection have at least one image so it's a bit too late for many things. Also we lost a lot of raw images due to an IT error. Thus, for these we only have jpegs.

- I have just started digitizing the *X* Invertebrate Collection over the past year with a NSF DigIn grant so imaging is a slow process right now. I hope to build more capacity to include more imaging in our workflows as we move forward.
- Switched from using Canon 5D and lightroom to a Sony Alpha7R...images so good we no longer need lightroom, so far. Image takes raw and jpg at some time.
- We are just beginning the digitization of our slide collection. We would be interested in accessing information about other microscopic slide digitization efforts.
- upload to SCAN arthropods/Symbiota but store images at our institution as well
- In this moments in the museum dont are digitalization of the specimens. Its a goals, but we dont have a tools, financial resources. The herbarium database its JACQ Virtual
- *X* was imaged because I participated in a NSF funded project in the MidAtlantic Consortium of Herbaria. I am not aware of the details of the imaging process
- The rate-limiting step in databasing (and curation) of our collections has always been lack of funding for curatorial staff: currently at 7.5 h/wk. Because of this there has been frequent staff turnover, which makes anything beyond the most basic training impractical.
- One of the biggest limitations in digitalization project is the lack of funding, in particular for small herbariums from developing countries
- We need every support
- great
- We have developed our own software for imaging. We have purchased a software called SCAN-CRAFT from Pune based agencies.
- Awareness, mobilization and support for institutions in Nigeria is necessary as most Herbarium/Natural History Collections aren't digitalized.
- Imaging at present is conducted on an as needs basis supporting loans and exchange and packet label imaging for transcription using DigiVol. Larger scale collection digitisation under consideration but unfunded at this time.
- Our catalogue is online at <https://fossil.swau.edu>.
- Small research institutions in Latin American countries only have access to free repositories of classic bibliography, digital collections and image banks. They generally cannot afford access to a number of documentary resources that are fee-based. This severely limits the development of research of the regional nature that requires comparison with nomenclatural types, classical bibliography or documentary images, for example. However, we are grateful for the opportunities that some image banks, museums and herbariums offer us from time to time. I pray for the growth of these resources and for their greater availability to all researchers. Good luck to you!

- This is a valuable activity, we understand that. Hopefully, there will be advances.
- I am not involved in caring for the collection which is presently mostly ignored at my institution.
- Digitization has been shut down since Mar. 2020 for covid, so I've forgotten things. We hope to resume next fall (funding/projects expired, but will continue with work-study student labor).
- As it stands, imaging our specimens has been a slow process as many of the objects have not even been entered into our digital catalog as well as many other issues with conservation. I have been on staff for a little over 7 years, and we are making significant strides, however there is still a long way to go. Until I started with the museum, less than 10 fossil photos had been taken and added to our digital catalog.
- We store herbarium specimens in polypropylene files and imagine them without drawing them out receiving good quality images
- Great to have all these image standards pulled together in one place! Now if I only had the staff/ to implement all these great ideas!
- A worldwide agreement is in urge to have standards and support to meet them in medium and low income countries.
- I am at a small, teaching-centered state college that has 2,000-3,000 (that's an approximation) herbarium specimens in our collection. This is not a research institution nor do we use these specimens for much other than teaching purposes. It is not within my time or expertise to do much with this collection.
- The *X* collection consists primarily of collections made during floristic surveys on military installations across the US. As such we need permission to make these public (scanned). Another factor is that funding was not set aside to scan these collections.
- There is no bird images available for the bird collection at *X*. I had my collection put on the web with VertNet about 2011 and then onto IDigBio about 2013 but have not updated it since 2015. There is no software here that allows images to be posted as I use Microsoft Access to keep the data. For other sections at the museum, any images are hosted by other institutions. Money, staff, equipment, and time are sorely lacking.
- We use to digitalize only as required for specific research goals, like a taxonomic review of a taxon, or for morphometric analyses. We don't have an institutional plan to create a repository of images associated with our collections (yet).
- With limited staff and resources we produce our images using an A3 scanner when time allows. If there is anything else we should be doing and are able to do we would like to know.
- Pensaba que la encuesta era mas corta. Nuestra especialidad son las colecciones, divulgación, cuidado y conservación, no lo que corresponde a la toma de fotografías y todo a lo que esto conlleva. Se hace lo que se puede, porque lo importante es la divulgación, el conocimiento es público.

- We have not imaged any other preparation types at this stage
- Nice survey. I like the diversity of standards presented. I'm exceptionally keen to have specimens digitized as a basis for identification for our citizen science platform (X), but unfortunately lack of support by local biodiversity organisations and total lack of funding prohibit us from addressing these most pressing of issues.
- Thank you for the website of the list of standards. And I will pay more attention on the detail of the progress of the digitization.
- The digitization of our specimens has been mostly carried out by the company Picturae as part of the network X
- It seems impossible to standardized and implement protocols for imaging wet marine invertebrates. There are just too many unstandardized variables with this diverse of a collection. The variations in size, shape, condition (wet/dry), etc. of a specimen alone make imaging challenging, time-consuming, and therefore cost-prohibitive. At least at this institution. We would require 4-5 total imaging stations (each for a different size) to accommodate the needs of the collection.
- Sorry, we do not do any imaging practices at this time.
- No comments.
- Happy to respond to such surveys. It would be better if iDigBio actually offered some help or outreach on these issues.
- Apologies for not having more information about our digital collection, as I was not involved in that process enough to know the particulars.
- I think this is a really great survey and I was happy to see the links for the imaging practices in with the types so I can now look at these.
- It is useful to know the results. It is not easy to do digitisation project for herbarium specimens and create a workflow for collections.
- For the last several years we (the herbarium) have only imaged on-demand and in low quantities, due to lack of finance (and priority). Since more then three years our collections are inaccessible to us due to an ongoing renovation of our herbarium building. Unfortunately we didn't received needed funds for a digitization effort during the renovation. There has been very little interest in large scale digitization (standards, best practice etc) from the muesum management.
- Main problem for imaging collection is being involved in a project with human time, there is no time nor priority for the current staff to both wrote projects and to practicaly digitise samples.
- Making the image is the 'easy' part... understanding how to store images,file them, database them and link them to other sources of information is the harder part... Integrating the disparate parts of digitising the collection at X will require someone with more specific IT skills than I have and a dedicated team of people to standardise the elements, back things up methodically et.c

- We may need some training on the standards protocols used for imaging herbarium specimens
- We image Natural History specimens as part of a whole-organisation approach to digitisation which includes everything from artworks to social history three-dimensional objects as well as documentary collections. As such equipment, workflow and prioritisation etc are influenced by a quite holistic approach. Our Natural History standards pay close attention to specific standards available, but we employ our own 'take' on them to fit within our workflow to better aid all of org digitisation.
- Lots of great resources out there, hard to pick. Great if there was a golden standard resources (like Darwin Core). Aware of Audobon Core, which is more metadata standards, great to have a overarching guide.
- We mainly use volunteers for imaging. Currently we are only doing ad hoc imaging as we investigate the possibility of mass digitisation.
- At the department level we were somehow aware of the importance of collection imaging. Unfortunately no initiative was taken in this direction, due to the lack of dedicated staff and equipment. Hopefully, with this survey we gained a better perspective and motivation.
- We serve and conserve digital image data generated over the last 20+ years that has been generated by more scanners, digital cameras, specialized microscopes, SEMs, and CT scanners than I can remember. It is hard to capture that kind of information in a survey like this.
- We also gather pics from the field, showing habitat details
- Interesting survey - well done.
- I am not an herbarium expert but I am now one of two individuals responsible for caring for the small herbarium at my institution. I am trying to begin digitization. This survey has made me realize I do not yet know enough about image standards, etc.
- It is good to have participated in this survey, I hope that by doing this, people from your institution will help us in the future to finish this undertaking
- To improve the quality and increase the scanned images of herbarium specimens, it would be advisable to buy a special herbarium scanner, but now it is quite expensive.
- In our collection, we focus on cataloguing. All new accessions (ca 5000 specimens yearly) are databased before being inserted into the collection. In addition, ca 7000 specimens are catalogued and georeferenced retrospectively and used from a national mapping project. There is absolutely no working capacity left for imaging.
- This survey opened my eyes to the many standards and aspects that need to be addressed when we embark on digitisation. That alone is significant and useful, regardless of the results of the survey.
- No great way to display micrographs in our public-facing specimen portals. It would be useful to stack images captured with different light sources but we don't support a tool that can do that.

- Since I do not work full time at the herbarium and another colleague does the digitization, I am unable to answer all the questions. Sorry.
- I do not know enough about imaging to answer your technical questions
- As you can see we have not started yet. And there is no light at the horizon.
- I am responsible for 40,000 lots of marine invertebrate specimens housed in a building that is located 5 miles away from my office. The fluid levels are topped off and broken lids replaced. Everything is labelled and catalogued. Effort to secure grant funding have failed due to lack of institutional support. My computer skills, including digital photography, are poor.
- We are a very small herbarium at an undergraduate only university.
- Check <https://webportal.specifycloud.org/shellmuseum/> for initial posted results
- I have been actively looking for opportunities to image specimens which are available on GBIF and CPNWH.
- Our collection will continue growing thanks to the remodeling of the Herbarium local, but digitization has been very difficult for us due to the lack of essential resources for it.
- We started a project to generate a low-cost protocol for 3D imaging of type specimens in a herpetological collection. Unfortunately it seems there is not community we can rely on so we basically have to start from scratch.
- It would be great if there were a way to share photographic equipment to perform this imaging. Or, a mobile group who would travel to take images.

7 Appendix 3 - Survey Questionnaire

Imaging Natural Science Collections Survey

1. INTRODUCTION

AIM

To build a comprehensive overview of awareness and implementation of standards, guidelines and protocols for imaging natural history specimens and to identify impediments that institutions face when imaging specimens to existing standards and making the images available online.

SCOPE

The survey covers all kinds of curated natural history specimens held in institutions (museums, botanical gardens, universities, research institutes, biological stations) across the world.

PARTICIPATION

In some institutions, it may be necessary for more than one person to complete the survey for different collections, whether by taxonomic group or preparation type. Where a single imaging protocol is being used for a preparation type across different taxonomic collections, these can be grouped into a single survey response. However, if different protocols are being used, then we ask you to respond separately for each.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

An anonymised, descriptive statistical report from the survey will be made openly available online. This report will form the basis of a joint MOBILISE/iDigBio workshop to be held in 2022.

SURVEY CONDUCTED BY:

MOBILISE, the EU COST Action CA17106 on “Mobilising Data, Experts and Policies in Scientific Collections”, part of the Research Infrastructure DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections. <https://www.mobilise-action.eu>

Integrated Digitized Biollections (iDigBio), the National Resource for Advancing Digitization of Biodiversity Collections (ADBC). <https://www.idigbio.org>

MOBILISE, the EU COST Action CA17106 on “Mobilising Data, Experts and Policies in Scientific Collections”, is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

iDigBio is funded by grants from the National Science Foundation [DBI-1115210 (2011-2018), DBI-1547229 (2016-2022), & DBI-2027654 (2021-2026)]. Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation.

ESTIMATED TIME TO COMPLETE:

The survey should take 5 to 10 minutes to complete per preparation type. You can choose to respond for a single preparation type, but if you have the time to respond

more than one that would be superb!

INSTITUTIONAL INFORMATION

* 1. In which country is your institution?

2. For which institution are you responding?

* 3. What is your role(s) within your institution? (check all that apply)

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Administrator | <input type="checkbox"/> Technical staff - digitiser |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Collection manager | <input type="checkbox"/> Technical staff - informatician |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Curator | <input type="checkbox"/> Researcher |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |

* 4. What is the estimated total number of specimens held in your institution as a whole (all collections)?

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="radio"/> less than 10 000 | <input type="radio"/> 1 million - less than 5 million |
| <input type="radio"/> 10 000 - less than 50 000 | <input type="radio"/> 5 million - less than 10 million |
| <input type="radio"/> 50 000 - less than 100 000 | <input type="radio"/> more than 10 million |
| <input type="radio"/> 100 000 - less than 500 000 | <input type="radio"/> Not known |
| <input type="radio"/> 500 000 - less than 1 million | |

IMAGING PRACTICES

*** 5. Standards awareness: Which of the following imaging standards/protocols/guidelines are you aware of? Please select all that apply. (A permanent link to these can be found here: <https://osf.io/eaz38/wiki/home>)**

- ALA Guidance: Digitisation: A strategic approach for natural history collections
<https://www.ala.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2011/10/Digitisation-guide-120223.pdf>
- Digital Preservation Coalition
<https://www.dpconline.org/handbook>
- FADGI (Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative)
<http://www.digitizationguidelines.gov>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.1: Quality Management Methodologies for Digitization Operations
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3469521>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.2: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of microscopic and other slides
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3364481>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.3: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of skins and other vertebrate material
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3364385>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.4: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of liquid samples
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3469547>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.5: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of pinned insects
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3520667>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.6: Best practice guidelines for imaging of herbarium specimens
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3524263>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.7: Rapid 3D capture methods in biological collections and related fields
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3469531>
- iDigBio Recommendations for the Acquisition, Processing, and Archiving of Digital Media
https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Recommendations_for_the_Acquisition,_Processing,_and_Archiving_of_Digital_Media
- iDigBio DROID 1 (Flat Sheets and Packets)
[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID1\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID1))
- iDigBio DROID 2 (Pinned Specimens in Trays and Drawers)
[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID2\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID2))
- iDigBio DROID 3 (Things in Spirits)
[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID3\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID3))
- iDigBio DROID 4 (3D objects in Trays)
[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID4\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID4))
- NYBG Herbarium Specimen Imaging: Standards and Suggestions
http://sweetgum.nybg.org/science/docs/Watson_iDigBio-Botany-2014-Workshop.pdf
- JSTOR Global Plants guidelines
<http://www.snsb.info/SNSBInfoOpenWiki/attach/Attachments/JSTOR-Plants-Handbook.pdf>
- UPDIG (Universal Photographic Digital Imaging Guidelines)
<http://www.updig.org/index.html>
- None of the above

Imaging Natural Science Collections Survey

2. RESPONSE FOR PREPARATION TYPE 1

Where a single imaging standard, protocol or guideline is being used for a preparation type across different taxonomic collections, these can be grouped into a single survey response. However, if different standards, protocols or guidelines are being used, then we ask you to respond separately for each.

*** 6. For which preparation type are you responding? (If you work with more than one preparation type - please use a separate survey response for each one)**

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="radio"/> Herbarium sheets | <input type="radio"/> Liquid preserved |
| <input type="radio"/> Microscope slides | <input type="radio"/> Fossils (2D) |
| <input type="radio"/> Dried and pinned | <input type="radio"/> Fossils (3D) |
| <input type="radio"/> Dried - not assembled (animal parts, shell, bone, skins, fungi, carpologic, ...) | <input type="radio"/> Geological macro-objects (cores, rocks, minerals, ...) |
| <input type="radio"/> Dried - assembled (taxidermy, assembled skeletons, ...) | <input type="radio"/> Geological micro-objects |
| <input type="radio"/> Other (please specify) | |

*** 7. For which collection / taxon group(s) are you responding? (Select all those for which you use identical standards and protocols. Please use a separate survey response for each preparation type for which you use different standards)**

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Botany / Algae / Fungi | <input type="checkbox"/> Paleontology (Vertebrates) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Zoology (Invertebrates) | <input type="checkbox"/> Paleontology (botany / algae / fungi) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Zoology (Vertebrates) | <input type="checkbox"/> Geology (including meteorites) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Paleontology (Invertebrates) | <input type="checkbox"/> Microorganisms |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |

*** 8. Approximately how many specimens of this preparation type AND protocol are you responding for? Please answer with a number or a range**

*** 9. Approximately how many of these specimens have been imaged? Please answer with a number or a range.**

STANDARDS AND GUIDELINES

* 10. **Standards use: Which of the following imaging standards/protocols/guidelines have you used? Please select all that apply.** You can find more information on these standards here: <https://osf.io/eaz38/wiki/home>

- ALA Guidance: Digitisation: A strategic approach for natural history collections
<https://www.ala.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2011/10/Digitisation-guide-120223.pdf>
- Digital Preservation Coalition
<https://www.dpconline.org/handbook>
- FADGI (Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative)
<http://www.digitizationguidelines.gov>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.1: Quality Management Methodologies for Digitization Operations
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3469521>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.2: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of microscopic and other slides
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3364481>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.3: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of skins and other vertebrate material
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3364385>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.4: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of liquid samples
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3469547>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.5: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of pinned insects
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3520667>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.6: Best practice guidelines for imaging of herbarium specimens
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3524263>
- ICEDIG Deliverable 3.7: Rapid 3D capture methods in biological collections and related fields
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3469531>
- iDigBio Recommendations for the Acquisition, Processing, and Archiving of Digital Media
https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Recommendations_for_the_Acquisition,_Processing,_and_Archiving_of_Digital_Media
- iDigBio DROID 1 (Flat Sheets and Packets)
[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID1\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID1))
- iDigBio DROID 2 (Pinned Specimens in Trays and Drawers)
[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID2\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID2))
- iDigBio DROID 3 (Things in Spirits)
[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID3\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID3))
- iDigBio DROID 4 (3D objects in Trays)
[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID4\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID4))
- NYBG Herbarium Specimen Imaging: Standards and Suggestions
http://sweetgum.nybg.org/science/docs/Watson_iDigBio-Botany-2014-Workshop.pdf
- JSTOR Global Plants guidelines
<http://www.snsb.info/SNSBInfoOpenWiki/attach/Attachments/JSTOR-Plants-Handbook.pdf>
- UPDIG (Universal Photographic Digital Imaging Guidelines)
<http://www.updig.org/index.html>
- Other (please specify and provide link if possible)
- None of the above

OBSTACLES TO USING EXISTING STANDARDS/PROTOCOLS/GUIDELINES FOR IMAGING

*** 11. For this preparation type, what are the major obstacles you are currently experiencing in using existing standards/protocols/guidelines?**

- Financial
- Not aware of any standards, guidelines or protocols
- Lack of staff time
- Lack of suitable equipment within institution
- Lack of expertise within insitution
- Too much pre-digitisation preparation and curation required
- Not a priority within institution
- No obstacles present
- Other (please specify)

FURTHER INFO ON THE SELECTED PREPARATION TYPE

The following subsections on image content, format, quality and metadata are optional.

IMAGE CONTENT

12. For this preparation type, which elements do you include in your images? (please select all that apply)

- 1D Barcode (e.g. Code 39)
- 2D Barcode (e.g. QR code)
- Catalogue number
- Colour chart
- Other (please specify)
- Institutional name/logo
- Label(s)
- Scale bar

13. For this preparation type, what kind of images are taken? (please select all that apply)

- Whole specimen overview image
- Individual images of specimen parts (e.g. eggs, fossil shells, disarticulated bones)
- Trait detail image
- Label only image
- 3D image
- Multispectral image
- Other (please specify)

14. Enter any additional information about image content here.

IMAGE FORMAT

15. For this preparation type, which image formats are kept? (please select all that apply)

- RAW
- TIFF
- JPEG
- JP2 (JPEG 2000)
- Other (please specify)
- 3D
- Stacked from multiple specimen depth images
- Tiled

16. Enter any additional information about image format here.

IMAGE QUALITY (FOR THE HIGHEST RESOLUTION IMAGES YOU KEEP)

17. Please provide a measure of the resolution/quality for the highest resolution images you KEEP for this preparation type as a measure of dpi, ppi, megapixels, etc. Please state which metric is being used in your response.

18. What colour depth (bit depth) are the images?

- 8 bit 12 bit 16 bit 24 bit 48 bit

Other (please specify)

19. What colour space is used?

- RGB sRGB CMYK

Other (please specify)

20. Is colour calibration carried out?

- Yes No

Other (please specify)

21. Is image sharpening carried out?

- Yes No

Other (please specify)

22. Is color correction carried out?

- Yes No

Other (please specify)

23. Are the images cropped?

- Yes No

Other (please specify)

24. Enter any additional information about image quality here.

IMAGE METADATA

25. Do you use a standard for your image metadata?

Audubon Core No standard

Other (please specify)

26. How do you store your image metadata? (please select all that apply)

EXIF

Separate from the image file, in a database

XMP

Separate from the image file, in a spreadsheet or csv

IPTC

Not stored

Other (please specify)

27. Please use this space to add any other information about the imaging of this preparation AND protocol type within your institution, or any other relevant information.

*** 28. Would you be willing to answer for another preparation type?**

Yes No

Imaging Natural Science Collections Survey

3. RESPONSE FOR PREPARATION TYPE 2

Where a single imaging standard, protocol or guideline is being used for a preparation type across different taxonomic collections, these can be grouped into a single survey response. However, if different standards, protocols or guidelines are being used, then we ask you to respond separately for each.

From here on 'REPONSE FOR PREPARATION TYPE 1' was repeated up to 10 times, allowing to answer for multiple preparation types.

Here ended the 10th preparation type

Imaging Natural Science Collections Survey

12. FEEDBACK

235. Please use this space to add any other information or comments you would like to share about this survey, imaging practices, ...

236. Please add your e-mail address if you would like to receive a survey report.

8 Appendix 4 - List of standards and guidelines

ALA Guidance: Digitisation: A strategic approach for natural history collections
<https://www.ala.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2011/10/Digitisation-guide-120223.pdf>
Date: Date: CSIRO 2012

Digital Preservation Coalition.
<https://www.dpconline.org/handbook>
Date: 2001, 2015 (2nd edition)

FADGI (Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative)
<http://www.digitizationguidelines.gov>
Date: 2007

ICEDIG Deliverable 3.1: Quality Management Methodologies for Digitization Operations.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3469521>
Date: September 30, 2019

ICEDIG Deliverable 3.2: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of microscopic and other slides.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3364481>
Date: April 30, 2019

ICEDIG Deliverable 3.3: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of skins and other vertebrate material.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3364385>
Date: May 31, 2019

ICEDIG Deliverable 3.4: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of liquid samples.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3469547>
Date: June 30, 2019

ICEDIG Deliverable 3.5: State of the art and perspectives on mass imaging of pinned insects.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3520667>
Date: October 28, 2019

ICEDIG Deliverable 3.6: Best practice guidelines for imaging of herbarium specimens.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3524263>
Date: October 31, 2019

ICEDIG Deliverable 3.7: Rapid 3D capture methods in biological collections and related fields.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3469531>

Date: September 30, 2019

iDigBio Recommendations for the Acquisition, Processing, and Archiving of Digital Media.

https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Recommendations_for_the_Acquisition,_Processing,_and_Archiving_of_Digital_Media

Date: September 2, 2015

iDigBio DROID 1 (Flat Sheets and Packets).

[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID1\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID1))

Date: May 2012

iDigBio DROID 2 (Pinned Specimens in Trays and Drawers).

[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID2\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID2))

Date: May 2012

iDigBio DROID 3 (Things in Spirits).

[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID3\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID3))

Date: May 2012

iDigBio DROID 4 (3D objects in Trays).

[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_\(DROID4\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/Developing_Robust_Object_to_Image_to_Data_(DROID4))

Date: May 2012

NYBG Herbarium Specimen Imaging: Standards and Suggestions.

http://sweetgum.nybg.org/science/docs/Watson_iDigBio-Botany-2014-Workshop.pdf

Date: July 30, 2014

JSTOR Global Plants guidelines.

<http://www.snsb.info/SNSBInfoOpenWiki/attach/Attachments/JSTOR-Plants-Handbook.pdf>

Date: June 6, 2011

UPDIG (Universal Photographic Digital Imaging Guidelines).

<http://www.updig.org/index.html>

Date: September 22, 2008